

**ASSESSING THE EFFECT OF MEAL SYSTEMS' CONTRIBUTION TO
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN DONOR-FUNDED PROJECTS: A CASE OF
IICD KARAMOJA**

By

LOGYEL JOHNSONIC

REG NO: VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE

**A RESEARCH PROPOSAL SUBMITTED TO THE FACULTY OF BUSINESS AND
MANAGEMENT IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTER'S IN MONITORING AND
EVALUATION AT VICTORIA UNIVERSITY**

JULY 2025

DECLARATION

I, Logyel Johnsonic with registration number VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE hereby declare that this proposal titled “Assessing the effect of MEAL Systems’ Contribution to Organizational Performance in Donor-Funded Projects: A Case of IICD Karamoja” is my original work and has not been submitted to any other university or institution for the award of any academic degree.

This research has been conducted in accordance with the academic and ethical guidelines of Victoria University Kampala. All sources of information used in this study have been duly acknowledged through proper referencing and citation.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

LOGYEL JOHNSONIC

(STUDENT)

APPROVAL

This is to certify that this research proposal titled “Assessing the effect of MEAL Systems’ Contribution to Organizational Performance in Donor-Funded Projects: A Case of IICD Karamoja” has been conducted under my guidance and supervision as the academic supervisor.

It is now due for submission to Victoria University Kampala in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of a master’s degree in Monitoring and Evaluation.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Name of Supervisor: Dr. **Bill Nkeeto, PhD**

Designation: **Dean Faculty of Business and Management**

Institution: Victoria University Kampala-Uganda.

DEDICATION

I wholeheartedly dedicate this research dissertation to my beloved wife, whose unwavering support, patience, and encouragement have been my pillar throughout this academic journey. Your love and belief in me have been my greatest motivation.

I also extend my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Bill Nkeeto (PhD) for the invaluable guidance, patience, and mentorship provided during this research. Your dedication and insightful feedback have been instrumental in shaping this study.

To both of you, I am truly grateful.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, I thank the Almighty God for granting me the strength, wisdom, and perseverance to complete this research.

I extend my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Bill Nkeeto (PhD) for his invaluable guidance, constructive feedback, and continuous support throughout this research journey. Your mentorship has been instrumental in shaping this study, and I deeply appreciate your dedication.

I am profoundly grateful to my dear wife for her unwavering support, encouragement, and patience. Your love and belief in me have been a source of motivation throughout this academic endeavor.

I also wish to acknowledge the management and staff of the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) for their cooperation and willingness to participate in this study. Your insights and contributions have been essential in making this research possible.

Lastly, I extend my appreciation to my family, friends, and colleagues who have supported me in various ways during this journey. Your encouragement and moral support have been truly invaluable.

Thank you all!

ABSTRACT

The study mainly aimed at Assessing the impact of MEAL Systems' Contribution to Organizational Performance in Donor-Funded Projects: A Case of IICD Karamoja, Uganda. The research is guided by the following specific objectives: (1) to assess the structure and implementation of MEAL systems at IICD; (2) to examine the influence of MEAL on project effectiveness and organizational performance; and (3) to explore how MEAL practices enhance accountability, stakeholder engagement, and learning.

The research adopted a mixed-methods research design which incorporated both qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. Primary data was gathered through surveys, key informant interviews, and focus group discussions with Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) staff and stakeholders, while secondary data was obtained from organizational reports and relevant literature. The study examined key MEAL components monitoring, evaluation, accountability, and learning and assessed their influence on project effectiveness, efficiency, sustainability, and overall organizational success.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION.....	i
APPROVAL.....	ii
DEDICATION.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	iv
ABSTRACT.....	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	vi
LIST OF TABLES.....	ix
LIST OF FIGURES.....	x
LISTS OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	xi
CHAPTER ONE.....	1
INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.0 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background of Study.....	1
1.1.1 Historical perspectives.....	1
1.1.2 Theoretical Perspective.....	2
1.1.3 Conceptual Background.....	3
1.1.4 Contextual background.....	5
1.2 Problem statement.....	6
1.3 Purpose of the Study.....	7
1.4 Objectives of the Study.....	7
1.5 Research Questions.....	7
1.6 Justification of the Study.....	7
1.7 Significance of the Study.....	8
1.8 Scope of the Study.....	9
1.8.1 Content Scope.....	9
1.8.2 Geographical Scope.....	10
1.8.3 Time Scope.....	10
1.8.4 Target Population.....	10
1.9 Operational Definitions of Terms and Concepts.....	10
CHAPTER TWO.....	12
LITERATURE REVIEW.....	12
2.0 Introduction.....	12
2.1 Theoretical Review.....	12

2.2	Conceptual Framework	15
2.3	Review of Related Literature	16
2.3.1	Structured implementations of MEAL systems	16
2.3.2	Dimension of performance of donor funded projects	20
2.3.3	Relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor funded projects.....	25
2.4	Literature gaps	28
2.5	Conclusion of Literature Review	30
CHAPTER THREE		32
METHODOLOGY		32
3.0	Introduction.....	32
3.1	Research approach.....	32
3.2	Research Design	33
3.3	Study Population.....	33
3.4	Sampling strategy.....	34
3.4.2	Sampling Procedure.....	34
3.4.3	Sampling Size and Composition	35
3.5	Data Collection Methods	35
3.6	Data Collection Instruments	36
3.7	Quality Control of Instruments	36
3.7.1	Validity of Data Collection Instruments.....	36
3.7.2	Reliability of Data collection instruments.....	37
3.8	Data Analysis	38
3.8.1	Quantitative Data Analysis.....	38
3.8.2	Qualitative Data Analysis	38
3.9	Ethical Considerations.....	39
3.10	Limitation of the Study.....	39
3.11	Dissemination of Results.....	39
CHAPTER FOUR:		40
4.0	Introduction.....	40
4.0.1	Demographic Characteristics of Respondents.....	40
4.0.3	Employment Status.....	43
Figure 9: Distribution of MEAL Planning Effectiveness (Q1.1).....		50

Research Question 2: What are the dimensions of performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?	54
Research Question 3: What is the relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?.....	58
CHAPTER FIVE	64
5.0 Introduction	64
5.0 Discussion of Findings	64
CHAPTER SIX	67
6.0 CONCLUSION	67
6.1 Recommendations	68
6.2 Limitations of the Study	69
REFERENCES	71
APPENDICES	75
APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE PROJECT BENEFICIARIES	75
SECTION A: BIO -DATA	76
SECTION B: Structured implementations of MEAL systems, Organization performances of donor funded projects.	77
Appendix II: Interview Guide for Key Informants Interviews (MEAL Officers, Managers, Donor Representatives and Field Coordinators)	79
APPENDEX III: WORK PLAN	81
APPENDEX VII: BUDGET	82
1. Introduction	83
2. Summary of Feedback and Compliance Actions	83
3. Conclusion	84

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Gender Distribution

Table 2: Age Group

Table 3: Highest Level of Education

Table 4: Employment Status

Table 5: Religious Affiliation

Table 6: Overall Working Experience

Table 7: Marital Status

Table 8: Annual Household Income

Table 9: Disability Status

Table 10: Population and Sample Size Table (Krejcie and Morgan)

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Conceptual framework showing relationship between monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning systems and Performance of Donor Funded Projects at IICD.

Figure 2: Logic Model

Figure 3: Distribution of MEAL Planning Effectiveness (Q1.1)

LISTS OF ABBREVIATIONS

AFREA	African Evaluation Association
CAHWs	Community Animal Health Workers
CVI	Content Validity Index
DQAs	Data Quality Assessments
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
HRO	Human Resource Officer
IICD	Institute for International Cooperation and Development
INGO	International Non-Governmental Organization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LNGO	Local Non-Governmental Organization
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MEAL	Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning
MIS	Management Information System
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPM	Office of the Prime Minister
PEPFAR	President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
QI	Quality Improvement
QoC	Quality of Care
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
UN	United Nations
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WUCs	Water User Committees

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

Understanding how Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems impact the organizational performance of donor-funded development projects, using the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja, Uganda as a case study. The discussion traces the evolution of MEAL practices globally, regionally, and locally to provide contextual grounding for the study. Therefore, this chapter presents the background of the study, the statement of the problem, the purpose, objectives, research questions, scope, and significance.

1.1 Background of Study

1.1.1 Historical perspectives

Internationally agreed development frameworks have long emphasized the significance of strong Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems as cornerstones for ensuring transparency, adaptive management, and results-oriented development. Landmark agreements such as the Monterrey Consensus (2002), the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness (2005) and the Busan Partnership for Effective Development Cooperation (2011) collectively champion the need for robust MEAL systems that go beyond data collection to enable genuine accountability and learning across development actors (Dawn & Nidhi, 2012).

Historically, in the past two decades governments and international development partners have moved away from tracking inputs and activities, towards assessing outcomes and long-term impacts. According to Teresa (2005), many OECD countries have reoriented their budgeting and public management systems around results. Consequently, the demand for robust MEAL capacities has surged, with MEAL now described as both a “growth industry” and a “public good” for development effectiveness. The World Bank’s 2000 Monitoring and Evaluation Improvement Programme serves as a key milestone in this shift. It moved beyond simple programmatic lending, demanding accountability for results from borrower countries and requiring them to institutionalize MEAL systems that could track outcomes rather than mere processes (World Bank, 2001). This evolution elevated MEAL from a peripheral function to a core strategic role in development planning and implementation. However, despite this global push, scholars such as

Leeuw (2001) caution that many development organizations still struggle to show tangible results. He argues that MEAL systems often exist in form but not in function serving donor compliance purposes rather than being integrated into decision-making or adaptive management. Without strong feedback loops, these systems risk becoming bureaucratic tools instead of transformative mechanisms for development.

On the African continent, the practice and professionalization of MEAL have grown steadily since the 1990s. Bashaka (2015) observes the emergence of over 30 national evaluation associations under the African Evaluation Association (AFREA), reflecting rising demand for MEAL as both a discipline and a profession. Yet, despite this momentum, integration remains shallow. Institutional and legal frameworks to support effective MEAL practices are often weak, and national systems tend to function in silos undermining the utility of data for learning and policy influence. In Uganda, these challenges are clearly visible. As Hauge (2003) points out, issues such as poor-quality or outdated data, gaps in performance tracking, and weak accountability structures continue to hamper the effectiveness of public MEAL systems. The World Bank Operations Evaluation Department (2001) further found that Uganda's MEAL efforts were heavily compliance-oriented focused more on satisfying reporting requirements than on generating actionable insights to improve program performance or policy design. Globally, even in regions with comparatively mature MEAL infrastructures such as Latin America and the Caribbean the systems are not always effective as management tools. According to a 2005 World Bank report, MEAL systems often operate in fragmented, duplicated ways, resulting in inefficiencies and critical information gaps. These gaps limit the systems' usefulness for budget planning and strategic decision-making, reflecting a mismatch between what data is produced and what is needed (World Bank, 2005).

1.1.2 Theoretical Perspective

This study is anchored in the Logic Model framework developed by Patton (2008), which provides a structured and systematic representation of the logical flow between program resources (inputs), activities, outputs, outcomes, and long-term impacts. It visualizes how interventions are designed to produce change and guides both implementation and evaluation processes. The model's relevance lies in its ability to enhance organizational performance by making explicit the causal pathways through which program activities lead to intended results. In the context of this study "Evaluating the Impact of MEAL Systems on the Organizational Performance of Donor-Funded

Projects: A Case of the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD)” Patton’s Logic Model provides a conceptual and operational framework for assessing how effectively MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning) systems are integrated within IICD’s project cycle management, particularly in donor-funded programming in the Karamoja sub-region.

The Logic Model supports an evaluation of the internal coherence and functional effectiveness of MEAL systems within IICD. This includes assessing the appropriateness of performance indicators, the validity of data sources, and the feedback loops that enable real-time learning and performance improvement. As pointed out in literature (Leeuw, 2001; Teresa, 2005), development organizations often struggle to demonstrate tangible outcomes, and this challenge is amplified in fragile or under-resourced settings like Karamoja. The Logic Model becomes a critical tool in diagnosing these gaps and guiding strategic adjustments. Furthermore, the Logic Model is particularly relevant in exploring the linkages between MEAL system quality and organizational performance outcomes, such as program effectiveness, efficiency, sustainability, and stakeholder trust. It allows the study to interrogate whether IICD’s MEAL functions are strategically contributing to improved service delivery, adaptive management, and long-term impact a key concern for donor accountability. Finally, by applying Patton’s Logic Model, the study will be able to evaluate not only the design and operationalization of MEAL systems at IICD but also their transformative potential in improving the organization’s performance in complex development environments. It will serve as a guiding tool to examine how well MEAL systems are institutionalized, how they influence decision-making, and how they foster continuous learning and innovation in donor-funded projects.

1.1.3 Conceptual Background

This study focused on evaluating the impact of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems on the organizational performance of donor-funded projects, using the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) as a case study. The MEAL system will be conceptualized along three primary dimensions: planning and implementation, quality assurance mechanisms, and information sharing and utilization for decision-making and learning. The MEAL system represents an evolution from traditional Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) by incorporating accountability to stakeholders especially project participants and fostering

organizational learning as a critical component of adaptive management. In donor-funded environments such as those in the Karamoja sub-region, MEAL systems play a pivotal role in driving performance by enabling organizations to track progress, assess outcomes, and adjust interventions to respond effectively to emerging needs and contextual realities. A project, as defined by Malsam (2023), consists of a series of tasks designed to achieve specific goals within a defined timeframe, led by a project manager who is responsible for planning, scheduling, implementation, and tracking progress. The performance of such projects, particularly those implemented by development organizations like IICD, is measured by the degree to which they meet intended objectives while staying within the constraints of time, budget, and quality (Hazir, 2018). Monitoring in this context refers to the continuous and systematic collection of data related to predefined indicators. It enables project teams to track the delivery of inputs, execution of activities, and realization of outputs against initial plans. According to Omonyo (2015), monitoring supports operational decision-making by providing real-time feedback on performance, resource use, and potential implementation challenges. Evaluation, on the other hand, is a periodic process aimed at assessing the efficiency, effectiveness, relevance, and sustainability of interventions. Evaluations provide evidence-based insights that help organizations like IICD understand the degree to which project outcomes have been achieved and what adjustments are necessary to improve future performance. Both formative and summative evaluations contribute to organizational learning, strategic planning, and donor accountability (Omonyo, 2015; Hazir, 2018). Accountability and learning key elements in the MEAL system enhance transparency, participatory decision-making, and continuous improvement. In resource-constrained contexts like Karamoja, where donor expectations are high and socio-political dynamics (such as reduced foreign aid due to controversial legislative decisions) can affect funding flows, MEAL systems become central to demonstrating value for money, sustaining donor confidence, and building local ownership. The concept of performance in this study goes beyond project completion to include progress toward achieving results that are sustainable, appropriate, effective, and efficient. As the Handbook for Monitoring and Evaluation for Results suggests, performance is increasingly judged by an organization's ability to use credible data and learning processes to inform implementation, scale innovations, and adapt to shifting environments. IICD's performance in managing donor-funded projects, therefore, will be analyzed through the lens of how well its MEAL systems generate and use evidence to optimize project results. In summary, the study conceptualizes MEAL

systems as strategic enablers of high-performing development organizations. Through rigorous monitoring, purposeful evaluation, stakeholder-centered accountability, and adaptive learning, MEAL systems provide the foundation for delivering impactful and resilient donor-funded programs particularly in fragile and underserved regions like Karamoja.

1.1.4 Contextual background

The Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) operates within the socio-economic context of Uganda, where it implements programs that focus on key development areas such as Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) agricultural development, child protection, livestock, education, skilling and community empowerment. These focus areas are critical for addressing Uganda's development challenges, particularly in rural and underserved regions, where poverty, food insecurity, and lack of access to clean water remain widespread. IICD's programs are designed to contribute to improving the livelihoods of vulnerable populations, enhancing environmental sustainability, and building resilient communities. However, despite the organization's commitment to impact-driven programming, it faces several challenges in effectively implementing and utilizing Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) frameworks that are essential for measuring success and improving performance. There is often a shortage of qualified personnel with the necessary expertise in data collection, analysis, and reporting required for robust monitoring and evaluation (OECD, 2020). This capacity gap can result in ineffective tracking of progress and delays in identifying areas that need improvement or adjustment. According to recent research by Gustavsson et al. (2021), many NGOs and development organizations in sub-Saharan Africa face similar challenges related to the scarcity of skilled personnel, which directly impacts their ability to measure and assess project outcomes accurately. In Uganda, many rural areas where IICD operates face limited internet connectivity, power outages, and insufficient access to advanced software and tools for data management. As a result, data collection, analysis, and reporting are often hindered, leading to delays and inefficiencies in program implementation (UNDP, 2022). The World Bank (2020) highlights how the digital divide affects the adoption of technological tools in development work, especially in low-resource settings, and underscores the need for improved infrastructure to facilitate the use of technology in program management and monitoring. Lastly, resistance to accountability frameworks is another barrier that IICD faces in implementing MEAL effectively. In many development organizations, there is often a lack of ownership and engagement from staff and

stakeholders, especially when it comes to transparency and holding individuals and teams accountable for outcomes (Kusek & Rist, 2020). IICD is no exception, as there may be challenges in ensuring that all staff are committed to rigorous accountability measures, particularly in contexts where there is mistrust or where local power dynamics can influence decision-making processes. A study by Brock et al. (2021) explores the issue of accountability within NGOs in sub-Saharan Africa, noting that while accountability is crucial for improving transparency and fostering trust among stakeholders, it often faces resistance due to ingrained cultural and institutional barriers.

1.2 Problem statement

Despite the widespread adoption of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems by development organizations globally, A significant proportion of projects carried out by International Non-Governmental Organizations (INGOs), Local Non-Governmental Organizations (LNGOs), and United Nations (UN) agencies in Yemen exhibit inadequate performance (Lashuel,2022) show that many donor-funded projects often face delays, require extensions, or fail to meet intended objectives within set timelines and budgets. While data is routinely collected, the challenge lies in how well MEAL systems are implemented and, more importantly, how their results are used to guide decision-making and enhance project effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability. At the local level, the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD), like many organizations operating in fragile and resource-constrained contexts such as the Karamoja sub-region of Uganda, has integrated MEAL systems into its donor-funded programming. However, there is limited empirical evidence to demonstrate how these systems influence organizational performance. While anecdotal evidence suggests that MEAL systems generate useful data, the extent to which this data is utilized to improve project outcomes, foster accountability, and drive learning remains unclear. Moreover, no specific studies have examined the effect of MEAL systems on project performance within IICD operations in Karamoja. This gap in local literature and empirical assessment limits the ability to draw actionable insights and optimize project impact. Therefore, this study seeks to evaluate the impact of MEAL systems on the performance of donor-funded projects at IICD, with a focus on understanding how the structure, implementation, and use of MEAL outputs contribute to improved project outcomes.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess the contribution of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems to the organizational performance of donor-funded projects, using the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja as a case study. Although MEAL systems have increasingly been emphasized as critical tools for enhancing project quality and accountability, there was limited empirical evidence on their direct impact on organizational performance in remote and resource-constrained settings such as Karamoja. This study aimed to fill that gap by examining how MEAL practices influenced efficiency, effectiveness, learning, and compliance with donor requirements. The research provided practical insights that informed strategic decision-making, resource allocation, and continuous improvement within IICD and similar development organizations. Ultimately, the study contributed to the broader discourse on results-based management and sustainable development outcomes in donor-funded interventions.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives: -

- i. To assess the structured implementations of MEAL systems at IICD in Karamoja
- ii. To evaluate dimension of performance of donor funded projects at IICD in Karamoja
- iii. To establish the relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor funded projects at IICD in Karamoja.

1.5 Research Questions

This study answered the following research questions:

- i. What are the structured implementations of MEAL systems at IICD in Karamoja?
- ii. What are the dimensions of performance of donor funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?
- iii. What is the relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?

1.6 Justification of the Study

The recent suspension of USAID funding, initiated by Executive Order 14169 on January 20, 2025, has precipitated a significant health crisis in Uganda, with the Karamoja region being notably

affected. This abrupt funding halt has led to the loss of over Shs604 billion earmarked for critical health programs, including HIV/AIDS (Shs243.2 billion), malaria (Shs121 billion), tuberculosis (Shs60.2 billion), and human resource support (Shs67.8 billion). Consequently, more than 2,000 health workers have lost their jobs, severely disrupting the delivery of essential health services. In regions like Karamoja, where health indicators are already below national averages, the impact is profound. The disruption of services has not only jeopardized the health outcomes of vulnerable populations but also undermined the trust and commitment of donors, leading to a reevaluation of funding priorities. Despite the presence of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems within organizations like the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD), the continued underperformance of health projects suggests systemic issues in the functionality and effectiveness of these systems. Ineffective MEAL systems fail to provide timely, accurate data necessary for informed decision-making, adaptive programming, and demonstrating tangible impact, thereby exacerbating the challenges faced in the current funding climate. The rationale for this study is to critically assess the effectiveness of MEAL systems within IICD's donor-funded health projects in the Karamoja region. By identifying gaps and challenges within these systems, the study aims to provide actionable recommendations to enhance project performance, ensure efficient utilization of donor funds, and rebuild donor confidence. This is particularly crucial in the wake of significant funding cuts, where demonstrating impact and accountability is paramount to securing sustained support.

1.7 Significance of the Study

This study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) practices by providing empirical evidence of their impact on the performance of donor-funded development projects in a fragile and marginalized region Karamoja, Uganda. By focusing on the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) and other key actors in Karamoja, this research will generate localized insights into the implementation, effectiveness, and challenges of MEAL systems. It will also fill critical knowledge gaps in the current literature by exploring how MEAL contributes to organizational learning, performance, and community outcomes in a post-conflict, low-resource setting. The findings of this study will have significant policy relevance for both national and international stakeholders involved in development programming in Uganda and the broader East African region. By identifying effective MEAL practices and institutional barriers in the Karamoja context,

the study will inform the design of more responsive and impactful policy frameworks. Government ministries such as the Office of the Prime Minister (OPM), local governments, development partners, and donors such as USAID, EU, and FAO can leverage the findings to enhance accountability, learning, and sustainability in the delivery of services and resources under initiatives like the Parish Development Model and Uganda Vision 2040. For project managers, MEAL officers, and implementers working in Karamoja, the study will offer practical recommendations to improve program planning, implementation, and adaptive management. Drawing lessons from interventions like the USAID-funded Apolou Project, the research will identify best practices in MEAL integration and spotlight common challenges such as data quality issues, limited community engagement, and under-utilization of evidence in decision-making. These lessons can support project teams to strengthen internal systems and improve development outcomes. Given the limited technical capacity in remote areas like Karamoja, this study will advocate targeted capacity-building initiatives to strengthen MEAL competencies among local government personnel, community-based organizations, and NGO staff. Improved capacity will enhance data-driven decision-making, encourage participatory M&E practices, and foster a culture of learning and accountability, ensuring that MEAL becomes an integral part of organizational performance in the region. This research will highlight the role of MEAL in promoting the long-term sustainability of development projects in Karamoja. As seen in interventions such as Apolou and the Parish Development Model, projects that embed continuous learning and adaptive management are more likely to deliver lasting impact. By underscoring the importance of real-time monitoring, timely evaluations, and community feedback mechanisms, the study will contribute to more resilient programming and sustained improvements in livelihoods, food security, and service delivery across Karamoja.

1.8 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study was structured into four dimensions: geographical scope, time scope, content scope, and target population.

1.8.1 Content Scope

The research focused on evaluating the impact of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning systems on organizational performance. It examined how MEAL systems support project design, implementation, and adaptive learning; facilitate community feedback and stakeholder

participation; and promote transparency, accountability, and results-based management within Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD).

1.8.2 Geographical Scope

The study focused on Moroto District, located in the northeastern Karamoja sub-region of Uganda (Latitude: 2.53°N; Longitude: 34.67°E). Moroto is a representative district due to its long-standing development interventions, presence of multiple international NGOs, and IICD's operational concentration. Its unique socio-economic and cultural dynamics make it an appropriate setting for examining MEAL application in fragile, underdeveloped contexts.

1.8.3 Time Scope

The study covered a period of 5 months from March 2025 to July 2025. The period of 5 months was realistic for the research to examine how monitoring evaluation systems affect the performance of the Institute for International Cooperation and Development's (IICD) of donor-funded projects. This will be possible because data collection will be collected online.

1.8.4 Target Population

The study targeted a purposive sample of 196 respondents drawn from various stakeholders involved in project implementation and oversight. These include: IICD Staff source HRO (n = 100): Including MEAL officers, project managers, field coordinators, and technical leads involved in program implementation, Local Government Officials (n = 20): From Moroto District Planning Unit, Community Development Office, District Water Office, and District Health Office, Beneficiaries and Community Structures (n = 50): Including youth representatives, women's groups, Water User Committees (WUCs), Farmer Field Schools, and Community Animal Health Workers (CAHWs) engaged in IICD programs, Development Partners/Donor Representatives (n = 26). These respondents were selected through stratified purposive sampling and engaged through key informant interviews, focus group discussions, and document reviews to generate qualitative and quantitative data.

1.9 Operational Definitions of Terms and Concepts

Monitoring: Monitoring refers to the continuous and systematic process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data by the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) to

track progress, ensure accountability, and assess the achievement of project outputs and outcomes across its donor-funded interventions in Karamoja.

Evaluation: Evaluation is a time-bound, systematic, and objective process aimed at assessing the relevance, performance, efficiency, effectiveness, and sustainability of ongoing or completed projects implemented by IICD. It is conducted periodically to determine the value and impact of project interventions and to generate evidence for decision-making.

MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning) System: A MEAL system refers to a set of organized structures, tools, processes, plans, standards, strategies, indicators, reporting mechanisms, data management systems, accountability relationships, and learning practices that enable IICD to effectively monitor, evaluate, and derive insights from its programs. The system ensures stakeholder engagement, transparency, and the generation of timely, credible information for adaptive management and performance improvement.

Quality: In the context of this study, quality is defined as the extent to which the implementation of MEAL activities by IICD meets donor expectations and conforms to established industry standards, including timeliness, accuracy, relevance, and the utility of information for decision-making and organizational learning.

Results' Utilization: Results' utilization refers to the practical application of findings, data, and recommendations generated through MEAL activities to inform strategic and operational decision-making, improve project design and implementation, and enhance the overall performance, learning, and accountability of IICD's donor-funded projects.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter presents a review of existing literature and scholarly perspectives relevant to the study's core variables. It explores theoretical, empirical, and conceptual contributions regarding the role of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems in enhancing the performance of donor-funded development projects. The literature will be extracted from different books, journals, reports and other published documents by different scholars.

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Logic model

The Logic Model originated in the 1960s was developed by Edward Suchman and later refined by Carol Weiss Suchman's 1967 as a tool for program planning and evaluation, designed to clarify the logical sequence between resources, actions, and results. It breaks down a project into five interconnected components: inputs (resources), activities (actions), outputs (immediate deliverables), outcomes (short- and medium-term changes), and impact (long-term effects). In the context of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems and organizational performance in donor-funded development projects, the relevance of the Logic Model lies in its ability to create a shared understanding of how interventions are expected to lead to desired changes. It strengthens MEAL systems by providing a structured framework for tracking progress, ensuring accountability to donors, and informing decision-making. However, a weakness of the Logic Model is its often linear and simplistic design, which may fail to capture the complexity, feedback loops, and external influences that characterize development work. It may also overlook unintended outcomes or contextual changes. Nevertheless, the application of the Logic Model is widely recognized in donor-funded projects for planning, evaluating performance, and learning. It enhances organizational effectiveness by linking project-level monitoring to strategic objectives, ensuring that resources are aligned with goals, and that evidence-based adjustments are made throughout the project lifecycle to improve impact and sustainability.

The Logic Model consists of five main components: inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact. These elements are linked in a linear and causal sequence, allowing organizations to clearly articulate how specific investments and efforts are expected to lead to desired changes. In the context of MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning) systems, the model provides a framework for understanding how MEAL structures and processes contribute to the improved performance of donor-funded projects. Inputs refer to the resources invested in the MEAL system, such as human capital, MEAL frameworks, digital tools, capacity building, and donor funds. Activities encompass MEAL-related actions, including data collection, real-time monitoring, baseline and endline evaluations, learning sessions, and feedback mechanisms. Outputs are the immediate products of MEAL activities, such as monitoring reports, learning briefs, evaluation recommendations, and community feedback summaries. Outcomes represent the short- and medium-term changes resulting from the application of MEAL findings such as better decision-making, increased responsiveness to community needs, and improved project management and Impact reflects the long-term improvements in project performance, including increased efficiency, effectiveness, accountability, sustainability, and donor trust.

By applying the Logic Model to this study, IICD's MEAL systems are examined not merely as operational tools, but as critical enablers of results-driven programming. The model provides a theoretical basis to trace how MEAL inputs and processes lead to tangible and measurable performance outcomes within IICD's donor-funded projects in Karamoja. It also helps identify potential gaps where MEAL efforts may not be translating effectively into improved results. In essence, Weiss's Logic Model enables this study to assess whether and how MEAL systems are functioning as intended, and to generate evidence-based recommendations for strengthening MEAL practices that can enhance project outcomes and donor confidence in the Karamoja context.

Figure 1 The logic Model (Weiss, 1998)

Source Logic model (Weiss, 1998)

2.1.2 Results-Based Management (RBM) Theory

The Results-Based Management (RBM) Theory emerged in the 1990s as a strategic framework for improving public sector accountability and performance particularly in development and donor-funded initiatives. Rooted in performance management principles, RBM emphasizes the achievement of clearly defined results through a logical sequence of inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact (Binnendijk, 2000). The relevance of RBM to Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems lies in its structured approach to planning, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating development projects with a focus on achieving measurable change. It ensures that donor-funded organizations align resources with results, enabling better organizational performance, transparency, and accountability. However, a notable weakness of RBM is its overemphasis on linear logic and quantitative indicators, which may not fully capture complex, context-specific changes or the long-term social transformation often sought in development work (Holvoet & Renard, 2007). Despite this limitation, RBM is widely applied in MEAL systems to guide project design, track performance indicators, inform decision-making, and enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of interventions. It strengthens organizational performance by ensuring that learning is embedded into every stage of the project cycle, helping donor-funded programs remain adaptive, relevant, and impactful in diverse development settings.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

In this study, I used Weiss's Logic Model (1998) as a guide to understand how MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning) systems contribute to the performance of donor-funded projects, focusing on the work of the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja. The logic model helped to illustrate how structured MEAL processes can support an organization's ability to deliver effective, efficient, and sustainable results. The framework centers on three key aspects of MEAL systems, which I considered as the main drivers (independent variables) in this study: (1) MEAL Planning and Implementation – This includes the presence of clear MEAL plans, routine data collection, adequate staffing, and tools that guide day-to-day monitoring and evaluation activities. (2) Quality Assurance Mechanisms – These are processes like data quality checks, field verifications, internal reviews, and accountability tools that help ensure the reliability and accuracy of information collected. (3) Information Sharing and Use – This involves how the organization shares MEAL data with staff, communities, and donors, and how the information is used for learning, planning, and decision-making. I looked at how these MEAL components influence organizational performance the outcome (dependent variable) in this study especially in three areas: (I) Effectiveness: Whether the organization is achieving its intended project results (II) Efficiency: How well resources (time, money, staff) are being used; and (III) Sustainability: Whether the project outcomes are likely to continue beyond the life of donor funding. To make the relationships in the framework clearer, the study was guided by the following assumptions (hypotheses): H1: Projects with well-planned and effectively implemented MEAL systems are more likely to be effective, efficient, and sustainable, H2: Strong quality assurance mechanisms lead to better accountability and improved organizational performance, H3: When MEAL information is actively shared and used in decision-making, organizations adapt better and perform stronger over time.

In essence, this framework shows that MEAL isn't just about ticking donor boxes, it's about making data work for people. When MEAL systems are integrated meaningfully into how an organization functions, they become tools for learning, improving, and growing. In the challenging environment of Karamoja, where resources are limited and needs are high, such systems can make the difference between project activities that simply happen and those that truly create impact.

A simplified diagram of the framework is presented in Figure 1, showing how the three MEAL components connect to performance outcomes.

Source: Logical model (Weiss, 1998)

2.3 Review of Related Literature

2.3.1 Structured implementations of MEAL systems

In an article by Tache, (2012) on the important features of Logical Framework Approach (LFA) due to which the mentioned classical project management tool is lasting for more than 40 years in project management practice, proving to be a more requested instrument than ever by different international financing bodies. The article emphasizes the main elements of building a Logical Framework Matrix (LFM), highlighting its connexions with the process of project monitoring and evaluation. Also, the paper presents the main causes of recurrent failures of the method, and some improvement measures, so that LFA could become more powerful as a project management tool.

Under the recent circumstances of a more and more dynamic business environment, the method has undergone several recurrent failures, which made it vulnerable for the main stakeholders of the project. In this context, it is necessary to identify a set of strategic activities aimed to ensure the compatibility of the method with the main elements of companies' corporate culture (stakeholders' commitment, corporate social responsibility, organizational culture, business ethics, environmental commitment, social awareness).

Attainment of Kenya's Vision 2030 anchors significantly on the performance of the country's public servants. This understanding prompted the researcher to examine the influence of results-based management (RBM) on the performance of these public servants. The study undertook to establish the influence of target setting, work planning, monitoring and reporting, and performance appraisal on the public servants' performance. It also delved into the moderating effect of leadership on the relationship between RBM and this performance. The study followed a mixed methods research strategy that focused on an explanatory sequential design. Stratified random sampling was used to select 292, 156 and 136 respondents from the Ministry of Devolution and Planning, Ministry of Public Service and Ministry of Youth and Gender Affairs respectively. Purposive sampling was employed to select 15 key informants who were interviewed. The findings revealed that all the attributes of RBM had a significant and positive influence on performance thus: target setting showing ($\beta = 0.315$, $p = 0.00$); work planning ($\beta = 0.276$, $p = 0.00$); monitoring and reporting ($\beta = 0.212$, $p = 0.00$) and performance appraisal ($\beta = 0.216$, $p = 0.00$). Leadership was also found to have a positive and significant relationship with performance. However, the effect of leadership as a moderator was nominal. Overall, RBM was found to have a positive influence on the performance of the public servants. Thus, for improved performance, enhanced use of all the components of RBM is recommended.

In a study by Kihumbu, (2018) establish the factors influencing the implementation of Results Based Management in the United Nations Agencies in Nairobi. The study was guided by three research questions: The first question examined the effect of organization culture on the implementation of results-based management. The second question examined the effect of organization leadership on the implementation of results-based management, and the third question investigated the effect of organization resources on the implementation of results based management. The study adopted a descriptive study design, and a questionnaire was used as the

research instrument. This was used as the data collected was of quantitative nature. The target population was drawn from five UN Agencies in Nairobi, Gigiri complex consisting of 5 senior level managers, 10 middle level managers, 18, supervisors and 62 general staff. The study used stratified random sampling due to the heterogeneous nature of the target population. A sample of 77 was selected and 64 responded giving a response rate of 84%. A specifically designed structured questionnaire was the tool used to collect primary data for this study. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics including percentages and frequencies for easier interpretation. Pearson correlation and regression analysis were then used to show how the independent variables influence the dependent variables. Thereafter, the data further analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Software. The findings were presented using figures and tables. The study findings revealed that organization culture, organization leadership and organization resources have an influence on the implementation of Results Based Management (RBM). However, only organization culture and organization resources have a significant influence on the implementation of RBM. The findings show that organization culture has a high influence on the implementation of RBM. In addition, when organization culture is combined with organization resources, the resultant effect has a higher positive influence on the implementation of RBM. Organization leadership was found to have an insignificant influence on the implementation of RBM.

According to Olawale, (2012), this study evaluates the effects of project management on project success in Blackstone Construction Company. The study adopted a survey research design, using a combination of stratified and judgmental sampling techniques, A structured questionnaire was administered on 40 top and middle levels management staff of the company. The scales in the questionnaire were content validated and had a reliability correlation coefficient of 0.11. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-Square distribution. The research findings reveal that there is a relationship between project quality and business success, Project quality and technical success. The study also reveals that there is a significant relationship between Project cost and acceptability by clients. It was therefore recommended among others that total project cost on the side of clients should be minimized by ensuring that the project manager is innovative enough and creative in the apportionment of project cost without reducing the quality of the project.

According to Agaba, (2023) examined the effect of participatory project design on project success in a government-funded project in Uganda, a case study of Parish Development in Kabale District. A cross-sectional survey was done. 75 respondents provided information, and we integrated quantitative and qualitative analysis. The analysis was conducted on three separate levels and included descriptive, bivariate, and multivariate approaches. The bivariate correlations between the dependent variable and the predictor components were examined using a Pearson correlation matrix. The dependent variable was regressed against the revised predictor factors at the multivariate level (project success). An analysis of the data was done using a linear regression model. Results of the regression analysis demonstrate that participatory project design has a beneficial effect on the effectiveness of parish development models in the Kabale District (co-ef = -0.780, p-value = 0.000). The main conclusion of this study is that parish development model project success in Kabale district is significantly influenced by participatory project design. To guarantee the sustainability of the project success of the parish development model, the study suggests that more emphasis should be placed on adopting participatory project design through defining project goals, determining results, identifying risks and constraints, and refining project strategy.

In a study conducted by Ahumuza, (2024) on the effects of monitoring and evaluation on the success of government projects in Uganda. The study was guided by the result-based management theory as a resource management strategy. The theory has significant implications for strategic planning, monitoring and evaluation. RBM places the measurement of results at the heart of management. There are passionate debates about how useful or appropriate it is within social development. The study was guided by the following objectives: to examine the role of M&E team capacity and skills in successful implementation of projects, to examine the role of M&E transparency and accountability in successful implementation of projects and to examine the role of M&E participatory decision-making in success of projects. The study revealed that 36 (92.3%) of the study's respondents agreed that projects are completed on schedule and on budget, 2 (5%) were not sure with the statement while 1 (2.7%) disagreed with the statement. With respect to skilled monitoring personnel encourage diversity of thoughts and opinions, 29 (74.4%) of the respondents agreed to the statement, 8 (20.5%) were not sure however 2 (5.1%) disagreed with the statement. The study was conducted by Iganga municipality with a population of 39 respondents. The study revealed that monitoring and evaluation team capacity equips government with

appropriate monitoring and monitoring skills. The study furthermore recommends that in absence of monitoring and evaluation the, Iganga municipality programs will not achieve the set goals. The study observed that majority of the employees at Iganga municipality are female employees, so the study recommends Iganga chief executive officer to always consider gender balance among employees.

2.3.2 Dimension of performance of donor funded projects

In a study by Nyaberi, (2023) on the influence of project management practices on implementation of donor funded water and sanitation projects in the Central Rift region, Kenya. The study specifically sought to establish the influence of stakeholder involvement, project team training, monitoring and evaluation and risk management on implementation of donor funded water and sanitation projects in the Central Rift region, Kenya. The study was anchored on four theories, namely, stakeholder theory, team theory, dynamic capabilities theory and the theory of resilience. For purposes of this study, a descriptive survey design was employed. The target population was all 160 project members comprising project managers, consultants, project implementation teams and task managers from donor agencies in 16 donor funded water and sanitation projects in the central rift region. Using statistical formulae, a sample of 62 elements was obtained. Purposive sampling was then used in targeting the said staff in each of the donor funded water and sanitation projects. This study used questionnaires in collecting data from the target group. Pilot-test was conducted to check the reliability of the instruments used for data collection. Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. The study revealed that when all the variables for project management practices, stakeholder involvement, project team training, project evaluation and risk management, were multi regressed against the dependent variable, project implementation, there was an observable model of good fit at 99.6% hence, a good predictor of project implementation if cumulatively practiced. The study further found that stakeholder involvement is a significant predictor ($p=0.046<.05$) of project implementation in donor funded water and sanitation projects in the Central Rift region, Kenya. Further, the study established that project team training is an insignificant positive predictor ($p=0.800 >.05$) of project implementation. Project evaluation is a significant predictor ($p=0.024<.05$) of project implementation and role risk management was found to be a significant predictor ($p= 0.21 <05$) project implementation. Regression analysis

revealed that risk management variable ($\beta = 7.633$) has the greatest influence, followed by stakeholder engagement variable ($\beta = 1.192$) then followed by evaluation variable ($\beta = 0.116$) and lastly project team training variable ($\beta = -0.672$). Therefore, the study recommended that, project implementation teams for donor funded water and sanitation projects in Kenya should emphasize more on project risk management as it has the most significant influence on project implementation. The study recommends that the donors of the water projects should sustain project team training, as much as it does not significantly influence project implementation, but it contributes significantly to the overall model fit. The findings of this study will be significant to the government since it aims to stimulate economic growth through attaining value for money for funds sourced from donors. The study will also provide opportunities for project managers to identify key project management practices and how they influence implementation of donor funded water and sanitation projects.

According to Kiarie, (2016) revealed that Successful completion of a given donor funded project along the three critical dimensions of time, cost and quality, requires detailing all the planning requirements. In Kenya like other developing countries donor funded projects contributes significantly to the socio-economic development and growth. Achieving project completion on time within budget, at specified quality standards, and most importantly without unprecedented cost escalations is major criterion of success of a donor funded project. The general objective of this study was to examine the determinants of successful completion of donor funded projects in Kenya, a case of Turkana County. The specific objectives of this study were to examine; project procurement process and project planning tools on successful completion of donor funded projects. The study adopted a descriptive survey and census design method for data to be collected using questionnaires from 196 respondents. A pilot study was conducted to pretest the validity and reliability of instruments for data collection. The data was analyzed with help of SPSS version 22 and Excel. The study adopted regression analysis at .05 level of significance to determine magnitude and direction of the relationship of the variables under study. It was notable that there existed a strong positive relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables. The analysis showed that project procurement process had the strongest positive influence on completion of donor funded projects. In addition, project planning tools were positively correlated to completion of donor funded projects. Therefore, the most significant factor was project procurement process. This implies that these variables were very significant therefore needed to

be considered in any effort to boost completion of donor funded projects. The study therefore identifies variables as critical determinants of completion of donor funded projects.

In a study conducted by Odhiambo, (2020) it analyzed the critical success factors for the timely completion of World Bank projects in Kenya. The general objective of the study was to examine the critical success factors influencing timely completion of World Bankfinanced road projects implemented by Kenya National Highways Authority (KeNHA). The pragmatic research philosophy was used, and descriptive research design was adopted. The 340 World Bank-sponsored Road projects implemented by KeNHA selected through purposive sampling of trunk road projects were the target population of the study. The sample for this study was 20 projects which included completed and ongoing projects that have achieved 50% completion in the 2017-2020 fiscal years. The unit of observation was 52 managerial staff engaged in the execution of selected 20 projects. The data was collected through emailing structured questionnaires and face-to-face key informant interviews. The descriptive statistics used in analyzing the quantitative data were frequency distributions, mean, and standard deviation. Spearman rank correlation was used to determine the association between independent and dependent variables. The data was presented in tables and figures and supported by an interpretation from the researcher. The study was able to reach 51 respondents from the survey. The results revealed that project design, institutional environment, project management training, project coordination, and project monitoring all had a positive and statistically significant correlation with timely completion of projects. The study, therefore, concludes that limitations and challenges in the project design phase are more likely to contribute to timely completion of World Bank donor funded projects. That institutional environment of World Bank-funded Road projects had the least effect on the timely completion of road projects. That project coordination of activities was the most critical success factor contributing to timely completion of World Bank-funded Road projects with project monitoring becoming the third most critical success factor contributing to timely completion of World Bank-funded Road projects. The interviews supported the findings from the survey. These findings cement the importance of stakeholder theory in executing projects as communication and information sharing between parties in a project contributes to timely completion by improved coordination in monitoring, design, skills management, and planning of projects. It is this study's recommendation that independent project design consultants should be engaged in project design before the work begins. Regarding project coordination, the study recommends that land

acquisition be done immediately after designs are complete and prior to commencement of construction works and the challenges incurred during land acquisition will be avoided and this will enable the project to be completed on time, budget and quality. In reference to project monitoring, this process should be continuous and ongoing and not based on milestones but rather on schedules to be able to identify any time creep that may occur during a project.

According to Otundo, (2024), The empirical review of strategic intelligence systems and performance of donor-funded projects from a project management expertise point of view highlights the critical role of strategic intelligence systems in enhancing the success and effectiveness of such projects in Kenya's coast. The findings suggest that the implementation of strategic intelligence systems positively impacts the overall performance and outcomes of donor-funded projects, particularly in sectors such as education, healthcare, agriculture, water, and infrastructure. Project management experts emphasize the importance of utilizing strategic intelligence systems to gather, analyze, and disseminate relevant information for better decision-making, resource allocation, risk management, and monitoring of donor-funded projects. The use of intelligence systems enables project managers and stakeholders to anticipate challenges, identify opportunities, and make informed strategic decisions to achieve project goals and desired outcomes. Furthermore, the review underscores the need for continuous improvement and capacity building in project management practices, particularly in the context of donor-funded projects. Building expertise in strategic intelligence systems, along with strong project management skills, can enhance project performance, efficiency, and impact in the long term. Overall, the empirical evidence suggests that the integration of strategic intelligence systems into project management practices can contribute significantly to the successful implementation and sustainability of donor-funded projects in Kenya's coast, ultimately leading to positive social, economic, and developmental outcomes for local communities and beneficiaries.

According to Kanyi, (2023), in his study about capacity building and performance of donor-funded projects in Nairobi City County Kenya. Donor-funded projects have been associated with unprecedented delays, cost overruns, irregular scope changes, and beneficiary dissatisfaction which have been attributed to weak institutional human resource capabilities, and weak monitoring mechanisms. The goal of the study was to assess how capacity building affected the success of projects funded by donors in Nairobi County. The study sought to find out how technical

competence, managerial competence, and governance competence affected the performance of donor-funded projects in Nairobi County and was based on four theories: diffusion of innovation, transformational learning, resource dependency, and knowledge-based theories. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The target population was 55 donor-funded projects, and the units of observation were 311 project personnel. The research employed a purposive random sampling approach to picking 30% resulting in a sample of 94 people. This study's primary data included both quantitative and qualitative information. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in data analysis. Besides, multiple regression was used to determine the association between the dependent variables and the independent variable. The study revealed that technical, management, and governance competence all exhibited a favorable and significant influence on the success of donor-funded projects in Nairobi County. The study determined that staff training was in place among the projects, but it was not consistent and there was no policy to govern it. It is recommended that the management of donor-funded projects in Nairobi County should spend more on contemporary technology, innovation, and capacity to improve project efficiency and effectiveness.

In a study by Kalema, (2023) about factors influencing the effective implementation of M&E in Donor-funded Projects in Kampala Capital City Authority. The study objectives were: to examine how the project staff competencies influence the effective implementation of M&E in Donor-funded Projects, to assess the influence of budgetary allocations factors on the effective implementation of the M&E system in Donor-funded Projects, to determine the effect of donor influence on effective implementation of M&E system in Donor-funded Projects and to establish the influence of stakeholder engagements on effective implementation of M&E system in Donor-funded Projects in Kampala Capital City Authority. The study employed across-sectional design to obtain information from different stakeholders at Kampala Capital City Authority. A sample size of 80 participants was considered in this research, selected purposively and simple randomly. Using closed-end questionnaires, data was gathered from primary sources. Statistical Package for Social Scientists SPSS Ver. 25 was employed for data analysis. Findings revealed that budget allocation factors also had a significant effect on monitoring and evaluation implementation (Beta = .361; p-value <.05). Relatedly, Donor influence factors had a significant effect on monitoring and evaluation implementation (Beta= .362; p-value <.05). However, Project staff competencies had an insignificant effect on monitoring and evaluation implementation (Beta =.152; p-value

>.05). Stakeholder engagement did not have a significant effect on monitoring and evaluation implementation (Beta = .144; p-value >.05). Implementation of M&E under the KIIDP2 project was significantly influenced by budget allocation and donor influence factors as compared to project staff competences and stakeholder engagements. The study recommends that KCCA staff involved in the implementation of M&E should be given pre-project training before embarking on the KIIDP2 project. The study also recommends that stakeholders should ensure that the budget allocations and size for M&E activities in the KIIDP2 project are adequate.

2.3.3 Relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor funded projects

In a study by Abebe, (2023), assessed the effect of project monitoring and controlling practice on project success in the case of Ethiopian Airlines Digital PMO. To achieve the objective of the study Explanatory and Descriptive research design were used. As a result, the researcher mainly deployed quantitative type of research design. Data for the assessment is obtained through five-point Likert scale-based questionnaire from 43 selected respondents. Collected data was analyzed by using descriptive analysis, correlation and regression analysis using SPSS version 20.0. The results of the collected data show that there is good project monitoring and controlling practice in the organization, however relatively there is weak project change control process in the PMO. Results also revealed that Pearson correlation between project documentation processes was a moderate with project success, and Pearson correlation between project progress report process and project change control process was strong.

In a study conducted by Otundo, (2024), the effectiveness of donor-funded development projects hinges significantly on the implementation of robust Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems. Despite extensive investment in these projects, there is limited empirical evidence on how various MEAL components impact project performance, particularly in the context of Kwale County, Kenya. This study aims to bridge this gap by analyzing the relationship between MEAL practices and project outcomes in this region. Objective: The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the influence of MEAL effectiveness, training quality, community involvement, and resource availability on the performance of donor-funded projects in Kwale County. By identifying key factors that drive project success, the study seeks to provide actionable insights for enhancing project management and implementation strategies.

Methodology: The study employed a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. A sample of five donor-funded projects across various sectors-agriculture, water and sanitation, health, and economic development-was selected for analysis. Data on MEAL effectiveness, training quality, community involvement, and resource availability were collected through surveys and project reports. Linear and multiple regression analyses were conducted to determine the impact of these variables on project outcomes. **Findings:** The analysis revealed that MEAL effectiveness is a significant predictor of project success, with a strong positive correlation between effective MEAL practices and improved project outcomes. Community involvement also demonstrated a positive impact, though its significance was marginal. Training quality and resource availability showed less impact on project performance, suggesting that while these factors are important, their effects may be secondary to MEAL effectiveness and community engagement. **Conclusion:** The study concludes that prioritizing MEAL effectiveness is crucial for enhancing the performance of donor-funded projects. While community involvement is also important, it requires further optimization. Training quality and resource management, though less directly impactful, remain essential components of successful project implementation. These findings underscore the need for donor agencies and project managers to focus on strengthening MEAL systems and involving communities more effectively to achieve better development outcomes. **Recommendations:** The study recommends enhancing MEAL frameworks, strengthening community engagement strategies, improving training programs, and optimizing resource management. It also suggests ongoing monitoring and adaptive management to address challenges and ensure project success. **Future Research:** Future studies should explore the impact of community involvement on different project types, conduct longitudinal assessments of MEAL practices, and compare findings across regions. In-depth case studies and exploration of additional variables affecting project performance are also recommended.

In a study by Wanyoike, (2015) to determine the effects and influences of technical capacity, project planning and baseline studies for result based M&E on donor funded value chain projects in Kenya. In the research, donor funding for value chain projects has firmly focused on poverty reduction and improved livelihoods. The research targeted 200 value chain project staff from agencies operating across more than one county for over 4 years. Stratified random sampling was used to select 67 respondents. Pre-tested, structured questionnaires were used to collect data which

was analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. The study found that implementation, training and capacity for M&E were very important, 81.7% (49). Baseline studies were vital in designing and selecting project indicators, 76.6% (46). The study recommended building M&E capacities through training, regular reviews, adequate budgeting, thorough project planning, stakeholder involvement and participation in all project phases. The positive correlations between the independent variables further indicated that results based on M&E were influenced by a few factors which are interrelated and interdependent. The study concluded that technical capacity of M&E systems, project planning and baseline studies should be given priority for effective assessment of result-based M&E.

In a study a by Omwenga, (2024) examine the relationship between monitoring planning and implementation of donor funded agricultural projects in Kenya. The study also sought to establish the moderating effect of project environment on the relationship between monitoring planning and implementation of donor funded agricultural projects in Kenya. In the realm of donor-funded agricultural projects in Kenya, effective monitoring planning is integral to successful project implementation. Activities such as resource acquisition, organization of materials, and training farm operators depend on a well-structured plan. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN, 2014) emphasizes the need for a seamless integration of techniques, procedures, people, and systems rooted in thoughtful planning. This study employed a descriptive research design utilizing questionnaires as the primary data collection method, emphasizing a positivism philosophy grounded in quantifiable observations and statistical analysis. The target population encompassed various roles within donor-funded agricultural projects, totaling 383 individuals, with a sample size of 196 determined through simple random sampling. Reliability was assessed through a pilot test, utilizing Cronbach's Alpha, and statistical techniques were employed for data analysis, including descriptive statistics, multiple regression analysis, and statistical tests such as ANOVA. The study tested hypothesis related to the influence of monitoring planning on project implementation, as well as the moderating effect of the project environment. Findings: The study's statistical analyses reject the hypothesis (H01) that monitoring planning does not significantly influence the implementation of donor-funded agricultural projects in Kenya ($F(1, 155) = 70.985, p < 0.001$). Instead, it establishes a positive and substantial relationship between monitoring planning and project implementation, with monitoring planning explaining 31.4% of the variability in project outcomes ($R^2 = 0.314, p < 0.001$). Additionally, the second hypothesis (H02)

suggesting no significant moderating effect of project environment on the relationship between monitoring planning and project implementation is as well rejected ($F(2, 154) = 64.066, p < 0.001$), emphasizing the statistically significant influence of project environment dynamics on the effectiveness of monitoring planning strategies. Unique contribution to theory, practice and policy: Given that the study findings establish a positive and substantial relationship between monitoring planning, project environment and project implementation, it is recommended that project managers and stakeholders actively recognize and account for the influence of project environment dynamics on monitoring planning. This entails conducting comprehensive assessments to tailor monitoring plans to specific project contexts, fostering adaptability and responsiveness to varying conditions. By collectively defining and adhering to best practices the sector can enhance its ability to navigate diverse project environments effectively, ultimately contributing to the success of donor-funded agricultural projects in Kenya.

2.4 Literature gaps

A critical methodological gap evident across the reviewed literature on MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning) systems is the limited integration of rigorous and triangulated methodological approaches that could provide a more comprehensive understanding of MEAL implementation effectiveness. For instance, while Tache (2012) offers a theoretical and conceptual critique of the Logical Framework Approach (LFA), the study lacks empirical data and real-world application through field-based research, thereby limiting its practical relevance. Similarly, studies by Kihumbu (2018) and Olawale (2012) rely primarily on descriptive survey designs and quantitative questionnaires, which, while valuable, may not fully capture the complex, context-specific factors that influence MEAL system success. These designs often neglect the qualitative dimensions of stakeholder engagement, organizational dynamics, and decision-making behaviors, which are crucial for understanding MEAL in real project settings. Although Agaba (2023) and Ahumuza (2024) attempt to incorporate both quantitative and qualitative data, their sample sizes remain relatively small and are geographically restricted, undermining the generalizability of their findings. Moreover, some studies apply statistical methods like regression and correlation without addressing the causal mechanisms or longitudinal impact of MEAL activities. As a result, there is a need for mixed-methods research employing larger, diverse samples, longitudinal designs, and participatory techniques to assess not just whether MEAL

systems work, but how and why they succeed or fail across different organizational and cultural contexts.

The reviewed literature reveals a significant methodological gap characterized by an overdependence on quantitative approaches, particularly descriptive survey designs and regression analysis, with limited integration of qualitative or mixed methods designs. Most studies, including those by Nyaberi (2023), Kiarie (2016), Odhiambo (2020), Kanyi (2023), and Kalema (2023), relied heavily on structured questionnaires and statistical tools like SPSS, which, although useful for identifying relationships, lack the depth needed to explore complex, context-specific issues. For instance, Nyaberi's (2023) study did not include any qualitative triangulation despite dealing with multifaceted constructions, while Kanyi (2023) collected qualitative data but failed to demonstrate how it was analyzed or used. Similarly, Kalema's (2023) use of closed-ended tools in a cross-sectional design limited the expression of respondent experiences. Consequently, the lack of mixed-methods or qualitative techniques such as interviews, focus groups, or case studies restricts a deeper understanding of stakeholder dynamics, contextual barriers, and implementation challenges. Addressing this gap would enhance the comprehensiveness and contextual relevance of findings on donor-funded project performance.

A methodological gap emerges from the reviewed literature on the relationship between MEAL systems and the organizational performance of donor-funded projects, as most studies rely heavily on quantitative approaches with limited integration of qualitative or mixed-methods designs. For instance, Abebe (2023) utilized descriptive and explanatory research designs based solely on structured questionnaires and regression analysis, which limited the depth of contextual understanding regarding project monitoring practices. Similarly, Wanyoike (2015) and Omwenga (2024) adopted quantitative methodologies grounded in positivist paradigms, employing statistical tools like correlation, ANOVA, and regression analysis, yet failed to explore underlying perceptions, attitudes, or contextual barriers that influence MEAL implementation. Although Otundo (2024) adopted a mixed-methods approach, the qualitative aspect was minimally detailed, with no clear articulation of how qualitative data contributed to the findings. Across these studies, there is a notable absence of robust qualitative techniques such as interviews, focus groups, or case studies which are essential for unpacking the complex, dynamic nature of MEAL systems and their relationship with project outcomes. This overreliance on structured, numeric data restricts a

holistic understanding of organizational processes, stakeholder engagement, and implementation challenges. Addressing this methodological gap through the adoption of comprehensive mixed-methods or qualitative approaches would provide a more nuanced, contextually grounded insight into how MEAL systems impact the performance of donor-funded projects.

2.5 Conclusion of Literature Review

This chapter reviewed existing literature on Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems and their influence on the performance of donor-funded projects. The literature made it clear that while MEAL systems were widely promoted as essential tools in development work, there was still limited understanding of how they contributed to organizational performance particularly in complex environments such as Karamoja. The study was guided by two key theoretical models: Weiss's Logic Model and the Results-Based Management (RBM) framework. These models provided a basis for conceptualizing how MEAL components such as planning and implementation, quality assurance, and information use could influence project outcomes. However, both models were found to lean heavily on linear cause-and-effect assumptions, which did not always reflect the complexity of real-world development work. Recognizing these limitations, this study applied the models critically, using them more as guiding tools than rigid blueprints. The literature also revealed that although MEAL processes were mentioned in many development studies, few examined the direct relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance. Even fewer studies focused on fragile, underserved regions like Karamoja. This exposed a gap that the current study aimed to address—by going beyond generic discussions and focusing instead on how MEAL could enhance effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability in a specific, real-world context. To bridge this gap, the study developed a conceptual framework grounded in Weiss's Logic Model, tailored to examine the link between MEAL systems and organizational performance at IICD in Karamoja. The framework focused on three core MEAL dimensions and hypothesized that their effective implementation would lead to measurable improvements in performance outcomes. This framework also helped shape the research questions and guided the methodology in exploring the relationships in practical, context-sensitive ways. In conclusion, the literature provided valuable theoretical and empirical grounding, while also pointing out the limitations and gaps that this study sought to fill. The review strengthened the case for investigating how MEAL systems, when meaningfully implemented and used, could significantly improve the performance of donor-funded projects.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presented the methodology that was used to guide the study. It described the research approach, research design, study population, sampling techniques, sample size and selection, data collection methods, data collection instruments, procedures for data collection, validity and reliability of instruments, data analysis techniques, and the measurement of study variables. The methodology was designed to align with the study's main objective of assessing the impact of MEAL systems' contribution to organizational performance in donor-funded projects: a case of IICD Karamoja as a case study.

3.1 Research approach

This study adopted a quantitative-dominant mixed methods approach to guide both data collection and analysis. The quantitative component formed the core of the research, focusing on the collection and examination of numerical data related to the functionality of MEAL systems and their influence on the organizational performance of donor-funded projects. This included statistical analysis of structured responses from MEAL staff, project managers, and other stakeholders, enabling the researcher to draw measurable inferences regarding the relationship between MEAL systems and performance outcomes specifically effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability (Mugenda & Mugenda, 1999). To complement and enrich the quantitative findings, the study also incorporated selected qualitative elements. These were drawn from open-ended questions and informal insights gathered during data collection. The qualitative aspect aimed to capture practical experiences and perceptions around MEAL implementation offering a contextual understanding of how MEAL processes supported learning, adaptation, and decision-making at the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja (Arya & Yesh, 2001). Although the study did not frame explicit qualitative objectives, the inclusion of qualitative data helped to explain statistical patterns and provided real-world illustrations of the findings. This integrative approach was appropriate for a complex development environment like Karamoja, where understanding the "how" behind numbers is often as important as the numbers themselves.

The choice of this approach was justified by the study's goal to evaluate the impact rather than merely describe the existence of MEAL systems on organizational performance. It also allowed for greater validity and applicability of results by triangulating numeric trends with human insights.

3.2 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive research design, supported by a cross-sectional time frame. This design was selected because it allowed the researcher to systematically observe and describe the relationships between key variables namely, MEAL system components (planning, quality assurance, and information use) and organizational performance indicators (effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability) without manipulating any conditions (Ary & Yesh, 2001). Although the data were collected at a single point in time (cross-sectionally), the descriptive design enabled the study to quantify existing practices and measure the extent to which MEAL systems influenced donor-funded project performance at IICD in Karamoja. It also allowed for comparisons across different stakeholder groups involved in project implementation. The study further combined both quantitative and qualitative approaches under this design. While the quantitative component captured patterns, correlations, and statistical significance, the qualitative insights offered deeper explanations behind the numbers. This complementarity between methods enhanced the reliability and validity of the findings by reducing potential bias and providing a more holistic view of how MEAL systems operated in practice. This design was particularly relevant for development research where the goal is to not only measure outcomes but also to understand processes and identify areas for improvement within organizational systems.

3.3 Study Population

The study population was 196 which were comprised of staff and key stakeholders who were directly involved in the implementation and management of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems at the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in the Karamoja sub-region. These individuals played critical roles in planning, executing, and using MEAL processes across donor-funded projects. Specifically, the population included MEAL Officers, project managers, technical advisors, donor representatives, and selected project beneficiaries. Their inclusion was based on their practical experience with MEAL activities and their ability to provide informed perspectives on how MEAL systems

influenced organizational performance in terms of effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability. Engaging this diverse group ensured that the study captured a wide range of operational, technical, and strategic insights necessary to evaluate the actual impact of MEAL systems within IICD's programming in the Karamoja context.

3.3.1 Selection criteria

The study included MEAL Officers because they were at the forefront of designing and implementing monitoring frameworks, tracking key indicators, ensuring reports met donor requirements, and coordinating evaluations that informed project decisions. Quality Improvement and Knowledge Management Officers were also selected since they played a crucial role in promoting learning within the organization, capturing best practices, and helping the team continuously improve through regular feedback. Project beneficiaries were chosen because they directly experienced the services delivered by donor-funded projects and could offer valuable insights into how well these projects performed and how accountable they felt the organization was.

3.4 Sampling strategy

3.4.1 Sampling Technique

The study used a combination of simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Simple random sampling was applied to ensure high internal validity by giving every eligible participant an equal chance of being selected, which helped reduce potential biases from confounding variables. Purposive sampling was also employed to deliberately select key informants who could provide rich, detailed insights about the impact of MEAL systems, allowing the study to capture in-depth perspectives relevant to the research objectives.

3.4.2 Sampling Procedure

Project beneficiaries were selected using a random sampling technique, specifically the lottery method. Each member of the beneficiary population was assigned a number, and numbers were randomly drawn to ensure an unbiased selection. For the key informants MEAL Officers, project managers, project technical advisors, and donor representatives purposive sampling was applied. These individuals were chosen based on their roles and knowledge of how donor-funded projects

operated at the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja. Data from these participants were collected through face-to-face interviews.

3.4.3 Sampling Size and Composition

A total of 100 respondents participated in the study. This sample included 2 MEAL Officers, 2 project managers, 2 project technical advisors, 2 representatives of donors, and 92 project beneficiaries. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the key informants, while simple random sampling was applied for selecting the beneficiaries. The sample size was determined using Yamane’s (1967) formula to ensure it was statistically appropriate.

Table 1: Sample size determination

Category of Respondents	Sample size	Sampling Technique
MEAL Officers	02	Purposive sampling
Project managers	02	Purposive sampling
Representatives of donors	02	Purposive sampling
Project technical advisors	02	Purposive sampling
Project beneficiaries	92	Simple random sampling
Total	100	

Source: Primary Data (2025)

3.5 Data Collection Methods

3.5.1 Online structured survey

The study employed a structured online survey designed using KoBo Toolbox. This platform facilitated accurate and validated data collection through built-in features such as skip logic and field constraints. KoBo Toolbox proved suitable for real-time monitoring in remote and low-bandwidth environments like Karamoja, allowing for efficient data capture from dispersed respondents.

3.5.2 Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews were used as an exploratory method combining pre-determined open-ended questions with the flexibility to probe deeper based on the interviewee’s responses (Magaldi

& Berler, 2020). This approach enabled the researcher to collect rich qualitative data, explore emerging themes, and gain a deeper understanding of individual experiences and perspectives related to MEAL systems and organizational performance.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

3.6.1 Online questionnaire

An online questionnaire served as the main data collection tool for project beneficiaries under IICD's donor-funded projects. The survey link was shared through the official IICD MEAL WhatsApp Group, ensuring easy access for respondents, as all MEAL staff had regular data support and maintained digital connectivity. The questionnaire included both closed-ended questions for quantitative analysis and open-ended questions for qualitative insights. This structure enabled the collection of both numerical and descriptive data, which supported triangulation and strengthened the credibility of the findings.

3.6.2 Interview Guide

An interview guide was developed to facilitate semi-structured interviews with MEAL Officers, project managers, donor representatives, and project technical advisors. In line with Patton & Michael (2012), the guide acted as a conversational tool through which the researcher asked relevant open-ended questions aligned with the study's objectives. The responses gathered were later categorized into themes for analysis, allowing the researcher to capture nuanced views and deeper insights related to MEAL implementation and its effect on organizational performance.

3.7 Quality Control of Instruments

3.7.1 Validity of Data Collection Instruments

Validity referred to how accurately the data collection tools measured what they were intended to measure (Mugenda & Mugenda, 1999). To ensure this, the Content Validity Index (CVI) was computed. This involved expert judgment from the researcher's academic supervisor and two experienced MEAL professionals from IICD, who reviewed the questionnaire for relevance, clarity, and completeness. Their feedback guided necessary revisions to enhance the tool's alignment with the study objectives. The CVI was calculated following guidance from Burke (2000) and Amin (2005), where a CVI score of 0.7 or higher was considered acceptable. Based on

expert ratings, the final questionnaire achieved a CVI above this threshold, confirming that the instrument was valid for collecting reliable data.

$$\text{Content Validity Index (CVI)} = \frac{\text{Number of items regarded valid}}{\text{Total number of items}}$$

The instruments was therefore accepted to be valid if $CVI > 70\%$.

3.7.2 Reliability of Data collection instruments

Reliability referred to the extent to which the data collection instruments consistently yielded similar results when administered under similar conditions (Mugenda & Mugenda, 1999). It also reflected the dependability and stability of the responses obtained, as emphasized by Amin (2005). To assess the reliability of the tools, the researcher conducted a pre-test involving 15 respondents who were not part of the final study sample. This pre-test was essential in identifying ambiguous or unclear questions, which were then revised for clarity and appropriateness. The feedback from this process ensured that the instruments were well understood by the target respondents. Furthermore, the internal consistency of the questionnaire was measured using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, a statistical reliability test. This coefficient helped determine the extent to which items in the instrument measured the same construction. Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.7 or higher was considered acceptable for this study, indicating that the questionnaire was reliable and suitable for full-scale data collection.

$$a = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum \sigma k^2}{\sigma^2} \right)$$

Where σ = reliability of alpha coefficient

(Cronbach)

k = Number of items in the instrument

$\sum \sigma k^2$ = Variance of individual items σ^2 =

Variance of the total instrument

\sum = Summation

When the alpha coefficient is found to be 0.7 or above the instrument will be considered reliable to be used for data collection (Amin, 2005).

3.8 Data Analysis

3.8.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data collected from project beneficiaries were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25. Descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages, and means were used to summarize the data and provide an overview of demographic patterns and key MEAL system indicators. To explore the relationships between MEAL system variables (such as data quality, indicator tracking, and evaluation frequency) and organizational performance outcomes, Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted. This helped to determine the strength and direction of associations. Additionally, multiple linear regression analysis was employed to assess the predictive power of MEAL components on the performance of donor-funded projects at the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja. The credibility of the findings, consistent with the principles outlined by Punch (1998) and Creswell (2014).

3.8.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data collected through semi-structured interviews and open-ended survey questions were analyzed using a thematic approach. The researcher carefully reviewed and transcribed responses, then organized the data into emerging themes and patterns that reflected participants' experiences and perceptions related to MEAL systems and project performance. To support systematic analysis, the latest version of NVivo 14 software was used. This tool enabled the coding of interview transcripts and open-text responses, which facilitated identification of recurring concepts, comparison across respondent categories (MEAL Officers vs. beneficiaries), and development of thematic networks. This process helped to uncover contextual nuances behind the quantitative trends and allowed the study to go beyond the numbers to interpret the "why" and "how" behind stakeholder responses. The insights generated from qualitative data were triangulated with the quantitative findings for each research objective. This not only enhanced the validity of the results but also provided a richer, more comprehensive understanding of how MEAL systems influenced the organizational performance of donor-funded projects implemented by IICD in the Karamoja sub-region.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in strict compliance with ethical research standards. Before any data collection began, participants were fully informed about the purpose, scope, and expected outcomes of the study. An informed consent form was provided digitally and explained in clear language to ensure that respondents voluntarily agreed to take part in the research. To protect participant confidentiality, no names or personal identifiers were collected through the survey or interviews. All responses remained anonymous, and participants were assured that their privacy would be safeguarded throughout the research process. Approval of involvement of MEAL staff and beneficiaries in the study was formally sought and granted by the senior management of IICD. The researcher also adhered to the principle of non-maleficence by ensuring that participation in the study would not cause harm or distress to any respondent. Finally, all data collected were used exclusively for academic purposes and to support internal learning and program improvement within IICD. The findings contributed to a deeper understanding of how MEAL systems influence project performance and will inform future efforts to strengthen MEAL practices in donor-funded projects in Karamoja.

3.10 Limitation of the Study

The study faced some limitations, including (i) limited financial resources which restricted follow-up communications aimed at encouraging responses, and (ii) non-responsiveness from some participants due to competing work priorities despite repeated reminders. Efforts were made to minimize these challenges through flexible scheduling and clear communication with respondents.

3.11 Dissemination of Results

The final research report was submitted to Victoria University Kampala to fulfill the academic requirements. Copies were also shared with the senior management and relevant MEAL staff at IICD. Additionally, the findings were disseminated through internal learning workshops and published on IICD's online platforms to support ongoing project improvement and inform future MEAL practices.

CHAPTER FOUR: PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents and analyzes the findings of the study based on the three key objectives. The results are drawn from responses from 92 structured questionnaires and (8) eight Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS (v25), while qualitative data were thematically analyzed using NVivo (v14). The findings are categorized and discussed according to the three research objectives: (1) examining the structured implementation of MEAL systems at IICD, (2) assessing the performance dimensions of donor-funded projects, and (3) exploring the relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance at IICD.

4.0.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents.

This section presents a summary of the demographic characteristics of the 92 respondents who participated in the study. These individuals included both staff and beneficiaries engaged in donor-funded projects under the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in the Karamoja sub-region.

4.0.1.0 Gender Distribution

Table 2.0 Gender Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	65	70.70%
Female	27	29.30%
Total	92	100%

Among the respondents, male participants made up the majority, representing about (65)71% of the sample, while females accounted for (27) 29%. This gender imbalance may reflect broader structural dynamics in project staffing or

beneficiary selection, where men may hold a larger share of positions or have greater access to participate in development interventions. Nonetheless, both perspectives were captured to ensure a balanced understanding of experiences with MEAL systems.

Figure 2.0 Bar graph showing gender Distributions

4.0.1. Age Group

Table 3.0 Age Group

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
30 years & below	30	32.60%
31–40 years	45	48.90%
41–50 years	17	18.50%
Total	92	100%

The dominant age group was 31–40 years, comprising nearly (45) 49% of all respondents. Those aged 30 years and below followed closely at (30) 33%, and a smaller proportion, about (17) 19%, were aged 41–50 years. This spread suggests that most respondents were within their early to mid-career stages, a cohort typically active in both delivering and engaging with project interventions.

The relatively youthful nature of the participants likely contributed to digital responsiveness and openness to MEAL-related innovations.

Figure 2: Bar Chart showing Age Group

4.0.2. Educational Attainment

Table 4: Highest Level of Education

Education Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Certificate	7	7.60%
Diploma	25	27.20%
Bachelor’s Degree	35	38.00%
Postgraduate Diploma	15	16.30%
Master’s Degree	10	10.90%
Total	92	100%

Respondents were generally well educated, with a significant number holding a bachelor’s degree 35 (38%). Others reported having a Diploma 25 (27%), while 15 (16%) had completed a Postgraduate Diploma, and 10 (11%) had a Master’s degree. A small portion 7 (8%) had attained Certificate-level education. This academic background provided a strong foundation for

respondents to meaningfully engage with MEAL processes, analyze project outcomes, and provide quality feedback.

Figure: Bar chart showing Highest Level of Education.

4.0.3. Employment Status

Table 5: Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Full Time	35	38.00%
Contract or Temporary	40	43.50%
Part Time	17	18.50%
Total	92	100%

In terms of employment, Contract or Temporary workers made up the largest group (44%), followed by those employed on a Full-Time basis (38%), and Part-Time workers (18%). This indicates a high reliance on short-term staffing within project

structures, which may pose challenges in maintaining long-term institutional memory and consistency in MEAL implementation. However, the mix also offers flexibility in engaging specialized skills.

Figure 4: Bar chart showing employment status

4.0.5. Religious Affiliation

Table 6: Religious Affiliation

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Protestant	40	43.50%
Catholic	35	38.00%
Muslim	17	18.50%
Total	92	100%

The study captured diverse religious identities, with Protestants forming the largest group 40 (43%), followed by Catholics 35 (38%), and Muslims 17 (19%). This diversity reflects the cultural and social fabric of the Karamoja sub-region.

Understanding these affiliations is essential in tailoring MEAL approaches that respect community norms, values, and trust systems.

Figure 4: Abar Chart showing Religious Affiliations

4.0.6: Work Experience

Table 7: Overall Working Experience

Experience Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than 1 year	10	10.90%
1–5 years	55	59.80%
6–10 years	20	21.70%
10–15 years	7	7.60%
Total	92	100%

More than half of the participants (60%) reported having 1–5 years of work experience, while about 22% had been working for 6–10 years. A smaller number had less than a year or more than a decade of experience. This suggests that the majority were

relatively new or mid-level professionals, offering a blend of fresh insights and growing expertise in project implementation and monitoring.

Figure 5: Graph showing Overall working Experience

4.0.7: Marital Status

Table 7: Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Married	60	65.20%
Single	20	21.70%
Separated	6	6.50%
Widowed	4	4.30%
Divorced	2	2.20%
Total	92	100%

Many respondents 60 (65%) were married, with others identifying as single 20 (22%), separated (7%), widowed 4 (4%), or divorced 2 (2%). The predominance of married participants may speak to the stability or maturity of the study group, and possibly influences how they perceive project support, especially regarding family

well-being and livelihoods.

Figure 6: Abar chart showing Martal status

4.0.8: Annual Household Income

Table 8: Annual Household Income

Income Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low (UGX 500,000–2,000,000)	65	70.70%
Middle (UGX 2M–10M)	25	27.20%
High (Above UGX 10M)	2	2.20%
Total	92	100%

When asked about their household income, most respondents 65 (71%) reported being in the low-income bracket (UGX 500,000 – 2,000,000 per year). About 25 (27%) fell into the middle-income range (UGX 2 million – 10 million), while only 2 (2%) reported high-income levels (above

UGX 10 million). This income profile aligns with the socio-economic context of Karamoja and highlights the need for donor-funded programs to address issues of poverty and economic vulnerability.

Figure 8: Abar Chart showing annual Household income

4.0.9. Disability Status

Table 9: Disability Status

Disability Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	85	92.40%
Yes	7	7.60%
Total	92	100%

Only 7 out of 92 respondents, 7 (7.6%) reported having a disability, while the vast majority 85 (92.40%) did not. Including voices from people with disabilities is crucial in

evaluating the inclusiveness of MEAL systems and ensuring that feedback loops accommodate and reflects the experiences of marginalized groups.

Figure 7: A bar chart showing disability Status

Descriptive Statistics

The following table summarizes the responses for questions 1.1 to 1.10, focusing on the effectiveness and implementation of MEAL systems.

Table 10: Summaries of responses for Questions 1.1 to 1.10

Question	Metric	Value
1.1 MEAL Planning Effectiveness (1–5)	Mean (SD)	3.13 (0.89)
1.2 Report Sharing Frequency	Most Common	Monthly (46.7%, n=43)
1.3 Documented MEAL Framework	Yes	95.7% (n=88)
1.4 MEAL Tools Review Frequency	Most Common	Quarterly (50.0%, n=46)
1.5 MEAL Data Reliance (1–5)	Mean (SD)	3.89 (1.02)
1.6 MEAL Roles Clarity (1–3)	Most Common	Somewhat Clearly (67.4%, n=62)

1.7 Reflection Sessions Frequency	Most Common	Quarterly (60.9%, n=56)
1.8 Baseline Data Collection (1–4)	Most Common	Always (50.0%, n=46)
1.9 Data Disaggregation (1–2)	Always Comprehensively	88.0% (n=81)
1.10 Community Feedback Frequency	Most Common	Monthly (50.0%, n=46)

Key Observations:

- MEAL Planning Effectiveness (1.1): Rated moderately effectively (mean = 3.13), with 34.8% (n=32) rating it "Effective" or "Very Effective."
- Report Sharing (1.2): Monthly sharing is most common (46.7%), but 9.8% (n=9) report "Rarely" or "Never."
- MEAL Framework (1.3): 95.7% confirm a documented framework, indicating strong formalization.
- Data Disaggregation (1.9): 88.0% report comprehensive disaggregation, a notable strength

Visuals

Figure 8: Frequency of M&E Report Sharing (Q1.2)

Report Use

The distribution of responses regarding the frequency of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) report sharing indicates that structured reporting is a common practice among organizations. Nearly half of the respondents (46.7%) noted that M&E reports are disseminated monthly, suggesting that organizations value consistent and timely reporting that allows for both reflection and adaptive decision-making. A further 34.8% indicated that reporting is conducted quarterly, a practice that often aligns with donor requirements and organizational planning cycles. Collectively, these

findings highlight that over four-fifths of respondents (81.5%) adhere to structured and periodic reporting schedules, reinforcing the centrality of M&E systems in promoting accountability and learning.

In contrast, only 10.9% of respondents reported weekly sharing, which is less common and may be resource-intensive, potentially limiting in-depth data analysis. Additionally, 7.6% of respondents reported that M&E reports are shared rarely, underscoring inconsistencies in information flow that may impede organizational performance and stakeholder engagement. These

findings suggest that while most organizations have embedded M&E reporting into their systems, there remain areas requiring improvement to enhance timeliness and inclusiveness in information sharing.

Presentation/Meeting Use

The chart shows how often M&E reports are shared. Most organizations share reports **monthly (46.7%)** or **quarterly (34.8%)**, which means the majority follow regular reporting schedules. This helps ensure accountability and supports decision-making.

Only a small percentage share reports **weekly (10.9%)**, while **7.6%** said reports are shared **rarely**. This suggests that very frequent reporting is less practical, while infrequent reporting could limit transparency and learning.

Overall, the findings highlight that most organizations have strong reporting systems, but there's still a need to improve consistency, especially for those who rarely share reports.

Figure 9: Distribution of MEAL Planning Effectiveness (Q1.1)

Report Use

The histogram presents the distribution of Likert-scale responses regarding the perceived effectiveness of M&E practices. The results indicate that many respondents consider M&E systems to be functioning positively, with 37.0% rating them as moderately effective and 29.3% as effective. This suggests that over two-thirds (66.3%) of respondents perceive M&E as making meaningful contributions, though not necessarily at the highest level of effectiveness.

A further 25.0% rated the systems as slightly effective, reflecting moderate satisfaction but also highlighting areas for improvement in functionality and responsiveness. Meanwhile, a small proportion of respondents viewed the systems as performing at extremes: only 5.4% considered them very effective, while 3.3% indicated they were not effective. These findings point to a consensus that while M&E mechanisms are operational and contribute to project outcomes, there remain significant opportunities to enhance their efficiency, utilization, and impact.

Presentation/Meeting Use

The results show that most respondents believe M&E systems are working well. About 37% said they are moderately effective, and 29.3% said they are effective. This means over two-thirds of respondents see M&E as useful.

However, 25% felt M&E is only slightly effective, suggesting gaps in consistency and implementation. Very few respondents placed M&E at the extremes: 5.4% said it was very effective, while 3.3% said it was not effective at all.

In simple terms, most people believe M&E is helping, but there is room to strengthen the systems so that more stakeholders view them as highly effective.

Qualitative Integration under objective 1

Table 11: Qualitative Integration Themes & Evidence Table

Theme	Findings (from responses)	Enhancement/Quantitative Link
1. Setting Project Objectives & Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objectives set collaboratively with donors, technical teams, and communities. - Indicators derived from donor libraries (USAID, EU, UN) and adapted using SMART criteria. - Use of LFA and ToC frameworks. 	Supports moderate effectiveness rating (mean = 3.13). Explains why 34.8% rated “Effective/Very Effective.” Structured yet participatory design builds ownership.
2. Data Collection, Analysis & Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monthly, quarterly, annual data cycles. - Use of KoboToolbox, ODK, CommCare for mobile data collection. - Data disaggregated by sex, age, and location. - Processes include identifying gaps → SoW → data collection → analysis → reporting. 	Aligns with 46.7% monthly report sharing. Robust systems reflect 88% disaggregation rate, but “data gaps” highlight weaknesses explaining 37% “Moderately Effective.”
3. Data Quality Assurance & Verification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of DQA framework, RDVs, spot checks, and internal audits. - MEAL Officers conduct monthly verification visits using checklists. - Field monitoring visits enhance accuracy. 	Supports high disaggregation (88%) and proactive quality assurance. Helps mitigate weaknesses linked to rare/never reporting (9.8%).

Theme	Findings (from responses)	Enhancement/Quantitative Link
4. Documentation & Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lessons learned captured via AARs, reflection meetings, evaluations. - Documented in learning briefs, shared via Google Drive, SharePoint, forums. - Feedback also provided to communities. 	Aligns with 60.9% quarterly reflection sessions. Internal learning effective, but limited community feedback highlights gaps (50% monthly rate only).
5. Alignment of MEAL Tools with Donor & Community Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tools customized to donor requirements (e.g., USAID AMELP). - Participatory, translated into local languages, pre-tested. - Indicators aligned to activities and donor frameworks. 	Supports 95.7% documented framework rate. Enhances planning effectiveness (mean = 3.13). Strong donor-community alignment noted.
6. Building Staff Capacity in MEAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capacity built through training, workshops, online courses, mentorship, certifications. - Orientation for new staff; volunteers engaged. - Training on data tools supported by MEAL plans. 	Explains 67.4% “Somewhat Clearly” defined roles. Staff capacity building ongoing but requires scaling to improve reliance on MEAL data (m

Key Observations

Setting Project Objectives & Indicators

The findings reveal that project objectives and indicators at IICD are set collaboratively, involving donors, technical teams, and local stakeholders. Frameworks such as the Logical Framework Approach (LFA) and Theory of Change (ToC) are widely applied, with indicators adapted from donor libraries and aligned with Uganda’s national development priorities. This systematic yet participatory approach reflects a structured process that likely contributes to the moderate effectiveness rating (mean = 3.13). The collaborative design process may also explain why a significant proportion of respondents rated M&E systems as “Effective” or “Very Effective.”

Data Collection, Analysis & Reporting

Data collection and reporting at IICD follow a structured cycle, with monthly, quarterly, and annual processes in place. Digital tools such as KoboToolbox, ODK, and CommCare are widely used to enhance efficiency, while data is disaggregated by sex, age, and location. The processes outlined—gap identification, statement of work development, data collection, analysis, and dissemination—demonstrate systematic practice. These findings align with the quantitative evidence showing 46.7% monthly reporting and 88% disaggregation. However, references to “data gaps” suggest weaknesses that may account for the 37% of respondents rating the system as only moderately effective.

Data Quality Assurance & Verification

IICD demonstrates strong emphasis on data quality through the application of a Data Quality Assurance (DQA) framework, routine data verification (RDV), spot checks, and audits. MEAL Officers conduct monthly verification visits, assessing data against accuracy, timeliness, reliability, and completeness. This proactive approach to quality assurance supports the high disaggregation rate (88%) and strengthens system credibility. Such practices mitigate weaknesses that may otherwise explain the 9.8% of respondents who indicated reports are rarely or never shared.

Documentation & Learning

Lessons learned and best practices are systematically documented through After-Action Reviews, quarterly reflection meetings, and evaluations. These are consolidated into learning briefs and shared via online platforms such as Google Drive and SharePoint, as well as through stakeholder forums. Importantly, feedback loops extend to communities, though this remains less consistent. The 60.9% reporting quarterly reflection sessions supports the presence of effective internal learning. However, gaps in community feedback align with only 50% reporting monthly community-level information sharing, suggesting a need to strengthen participatory learning beyond the organization.

Alignment of MEAL Tools with Donor & Community Needs

The findings highlight that MEAL tools are customized to balance donor requirements and local contexts. Tools such as USAID’s PMP/AMELP are adapted, translated into local languages, and pre-tested for appropriateness, while indicators are disaggregated to reflect both donor and community needs. This dual alignment supports the high rate (95.7%) of documented frameworks and contributes to planning effectiveness (mean = 3.13). Such practices ensure that M&E systems are not only donor-compliant but also contextually relevant, enhancing inclusivity and usability.

Building Staff Capacity in MEAL

Staff capacity is enhanced through a range of initiatives, including in-house training, workshops, mentorship, and certifications. New staff undergo orientation, while ongoing training supports the use of digital data tools. Volunteers are also engaged to complement MEAL staff capacity. Despite these efforts, reliance on “somewhat clearly” defined roles (67.4%) suggests that training interventions, while present, are not yet sufficient to optimize system performance. This aligns with the relatively high mean score (3.89), pointing to positive but improvable investment in MEAL capacity building.

Research Question 2: What are the dimensions of performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?

Descriptive Statistics

The table below summarizes the responses for questions 2.1 to 2.8, evaluating project performance

Table 12: Summaries of responses for questions 2.1 to 2.8

Question	Metric	Value
2.1 Budget Satisfaction (1–4)	Mean (SD)	2.92 (0.76)
2.2 Goal Achievement (1–4)	Mean (SD)	2.18 (0.78)
2.3 Timeliness (1–4)	Mean (SD)	2.92 (0.44)
2.4 Monitoring Frequency	Most Common	Monthly (47.8%, n=44)

2.5 Communication Effectiveness (1–5)	Mean (SD)	3.72 (0.74)
2.6 Service Quality Satisfaction (1–4)	Mean (SD)	2.80 (0.80)
2.7 Beneficiary Involvement	Yes	76.1% (n=70)
2.8 Donor Report Timeliness	Most Common	Mostly on time (67.4%, n=62)

Key Observations:

- Budget Satisfaction (2.1): Moderate satisfaction (mean = 2.92), with 60.9% (n=56) "Satisfied" or "Very Satisfied."
- Goal Achievement (2.2): Projects achieve goals to "some extent" (mean = 2.18), with only 4.3% (n=4) reporting "To a greater extent."
- Timeliness (2.3): Rated "Good" by 75.0% (n=69), indicating strong performance in this area.
- Beneficiary Involvement (2.7): 76.1% confirm involvement, a positive indicator of participatory approaches.

Visuals

Figure 10: Beneficiary Involvement in Projects (Q2.7)

Figure 11: Distribution of Timeliness Ratings (Q2.3)

Qualitative Integration for objective 2

Table 12: Qualitative Integration Themes & Evidence Table

Theme	Findings (from responses)	Enhancement/Quantitative Link
1. Measuring Budget Utilization & Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tools include Budget vs Actual (BvA) reports, cost-per-beneficiary analysis, burn rate tracking, and quarterly financial dashboards. - Financial tracking reconciled with program outputs. 	Supports moderate satisfaction (mean = 2.92). Robust tools exist but budget constraints and inefficiencies may explain the moderate rating.
2. Assessing Goal, Output & Outcome Achievement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of IPTTs, baseline/midline/endline evaluations, community feedback, MSC stories, and routine field visits. - Comparison of targets vs. actuals. 	Aligns with moderate goal achievement (mean = 2.18). Despite comprehensive assessments, challenges such as “data gaps” hinder performance.
3. Indicators & Benchmarks for Deliverables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicators: activity completion rates, timeliness benchmarks, quality standards, LogFrame and AWP targets. - Projects designed with tailored outcome indicators. 	Explains 75% timeliness rating (“Good”) and 76.1% beneficiary involvement. Structured indicators enhance accountability and tracking.
4. Community Satisfaction & Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mechanisms include CFMs, satisfaction surveys, participatory methods (e.g., scorecards). 	Reinforces 76.1% involvement rate and mean = 2.80 for satisfaction. Strong

Theme	Findings (from responses)	Enhancement/Quantitative Link
	- Community feedback prioritized in decision-making.	engagement practices enhance performance but need broader reach.
5. High vs. Low Performance Case Examples	- High: Youth Skilling & Agribusiness Empowerment Initiative (YSAEI) excelled through partnerships, relevant curricula, responsive MEAL system. - Low: Resilient Livelihoods for Pastoralist Women (RLPW) underperformed due to procurement delays, insecurity, and poor coordination. - EU projects trained 750 youths in South Karamoja.	Provides context for moderate goal achievement (mean = 2.18). Demonstrates MEAL's role in high performance vs. external challenges in low performance.
6. Mechanisms for Timely & Quality Implementation	- Tools: DIPs, Gantt charts, quarterly reviews, SOPs, joint supervision, real-time dashboards, learning sessions. - IPTT updates tracked at project team level.	Supports 75% "Good" timeliness rating. Dashboards and real-time tracking strengthen accountability and efficiency.

Key observations

Measuring Budget Utilization & Efficiency

IICD employs several financial monitoring tools, including Budget vs Actual (BvA) reports, cost-per-beneficiary analyses, burn rate tracking, and quarterly dashboards, to ensure resources are effectively utilized. While these mechanisms provide a robust system for financial oversight, the quantitative findings (mean = 2.92) suggest that budget constraints and inefficiencies still pose challenges. This indicates that while technical tools are in place, structural or contextual barriers may reduce overall satisfaction with financial efficiency.

Assessing Goal, Output & Outcome Achievement

Goal achievement is assessed using IPTTs, baseline-to-endline evaluations, routine monitoring, and qualitative approaches such as MSC stories and community feedback. Targets are systematically compared to actuals, reflecting a comprehensive framework for performance tracking. However, the moderate achievement score (mean = 2.18) highlights persistent challenges such as data gaps and execution bottlenecks. This suggests that while assessment frameworks are well-developed, practical implementation difficulties constrain the achievement of intended outcomes.

Indicators & Benchmarks for Deliverables

Indicators for measuring deliverables include completion rates, timeliness benchmarks, quality standards, and LogFrame/AWP targets. Each project is tailored with outcome-specific indicators

to ensure accountability and alignment with planned deliverables. These findings align with the 75% timeliness rating and 76.1% beneficiary involvement, suggesting that structured benchmarks provide a strong framework for tracking and meeting deliverables within expected timelines.

Community Satisfaction & Engagement

Community satisfaction and engagement are factored into project performance measurement through CFMs, satisfaction surveys, and participatory tools such as community scorecards. Importantly, community feedback is not only collected but prioritized in decision-making, ensuring responsiveness. This reinforces the quantitative evidence showing a 76.1% involvement rate and a mean satisfaction score of 2.80. While engagement mechanisms appear strong, further efforts may be required to broaden participation and deepen accountability to communities.

High vs. Low Performance Case Examples

Examples from specific projects illustrate contrasting performance levels. The Youth Skilling and Agribusiness Empowerment Initiative (YSAEI) excelled due to strong partnerships, relevant curricula, and responsive MEAL systems. Conversely, the Resilient Livelihoods for Pastoralist Women (RLPW) struggled with procurement delays, insecurity, and coordination challenges, resulting in weaker performance. EU-supported youth skilling initiatives also demonstrated success, training 750 youths in South Karamoja. These cases contextualize the moderate mean score for goal achievement (2.18), highlighting MEAL’s role in enabling high performance while also emphasizing external constraints that hinder outcomes.

Mechanisms for Timely & Quality Implementation

Timely and quality implementation is promoted through a range of mechanisms, including DIPs, Gantt charts, SOPs, quarterly reviews, joint supervision, and real-time dashboards. IPTTs are also updated regularly at the project team level, ensuring that activities remain on track. These mechanisms support the quantitative evidence showing 75% of respondents rated timeliness as “Good.” The integration of dashboards and supervision practices enhances accountability, contributing to more effective project delivery.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?

Table 13: Integrated Findings – RQ3: Relationship between MEAL Systems and Organizational Performance

Theme/Dimension	Quantitative Findings	Interpretation & Integration
MEAL Enhances Effectiveness	Mean = 2.89 (SD = 0.76); 34.8% agree/strongly agree	Moderate agreement suggests MEAL structures exist but are not consistently leveraged to optimize project effectiveness.

Theme/Dimension	Quantitative Findings	Interpretation & Integration
M&E Improves Outcomes	96.7% (n=89) responded “Yes”	Strong consensus indicates MEAL is perceived as essential for improving project outcomes, aligning with best practices in results-based management.
Accountability	Mean = 2.66 (SD = 0.91)	MEAL contributes to accountability only “to some extent. Limited influence may stem from inconsistent data use or weak upward/downward accountability structures.
MEAL Data Use in Project Design	Mean = 3.37 (SD = 0.96)	Relatively higher scores suggest MEAL data is actively informing project design, enhancing alignment with donor priorities and contextual needs.
MEAL Enhances Learning	Mean = 2.67 (SD = 0.75)	Moderate role in organizational learning, indicating potential underutilization of reflection processes (e.g., AARs, learning briefs).
MEAL Enhances Donor Confidence	Mean = 2.36 (SD = 0.89)	Weakest link: donor confidence is not strongly boosted by MEAL, possibly due to perceived data quality gaps or inadequate dissemination of results.

Narrative Synthesis

MEAL and Project Effectiveness

The findings indicate moderate agreement that MEAL enhances project effectiveness (mean = 2.89), with only about one-third (34.8%) strongly endorsing this relationship. This suggests that while MEAL systems provide structured approaches (e.g., use of IPTTs, LogFrames, and DQAs from earlier findings), their influence on overall effectiveness is not fully optimized. Limited resources or uneven application across projects may reduce their impact on effectiveness.

MEAL and Outcomes

A striking 96.7% of respondents confirmed that M&E improves project outcomes, demonstrating a near-universal recognition of its value. This strong positive perception underscores the importance of MEAL in ensuring that project interventions are responsive, evidence-based, and results-oriented. This aligns with qualitative findings from RQ1 and RQ2, where MEAL systems facilitated stakeholder engagement, community satisfaction, and tracking of deliverables.

MEAL and Accountability

On accountability, the data reveals a modest role for MEAL (mean = 2.66). While MEAL systems introduce mechanisms such as Community Feedback Mechanisms (CFMs) and DQAs, these may not be consistently implemented or perceived as adequate for holding both project teams and

donors accountable. This suggests an opportunity for strengthening both upward accountability (to donors) and downward accountability (to communities).

MEAL Data Use in Design

One of the stronger findings (mean = 3.37) is that MEAL data significantly informs project design. This reinforces earlier evidence that IICD aligns project objectives with donor requirements and local needs using frameworks such as the Logical Framework Approach and Theory of Change. The active use of MEAL data in design highlights its strategic role in planning and adaptation, even where effectiveness and accountability remain moderate.

MEAL and Organizational Learning

The relatively modest mean score (2.67) indicates that MEAL is not fully leveraged for organizational learning. While mechanisms like After-Action Reviews (AARs) and quarterly reflection meetings exist, the extent to which these translate into adaptive practices across projects seems limited. This underlines a gap between data collection and actual institutional learning.

MEAL and Donor Confidence

The weakest observed relationship is between MEAL and donor confidence (mean = 2.36). Despite MEAL's central role in reporting and compliance, its contribution to donor trust appears limited. This may be linked to issues of data quality, timeliness, or the perceived relevance of findings to donor priorities. Strengthening evidence dissemination and improving transparency could enhance donor confidence in IICD's systems.

Summary of Narrative for Research Question 3

The findings from Research Question 3 highlight the perceived relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja.

The results show a moderate perception of MEAL effectiveness, with an average score of 2.89 (SD = 0.76). While a considerable proportion of respondents (34.8%, n=32) agreed or strongly agreed that MEAL enhances effectiveness, the majority expressed only partial agreement, suggesting room for strengthening MEAL's operational influence on project performance.

A particularly strong positive finding emerged regarding M&E outcomes (Q3.2), where 96.7% of respondents affirmed that M&E improves project outcomes. This indicates a high level of recognition of M&E as a vital driver of improved project performance and success.

In terms of accountability, MEAL systems were perceived as contributing to some extent (mean = 2.66, SD = 0.91). This finding suggests that while MEAL structures support transparency and responsibility, their application may not be robust enough to guarantee full accountability to stakeholders.

The use of MEAL data in project design and adaptation received a relatively higher rating (mean = 3.37, SD = 0.96), reflecting an appreciation of how evidence-based decision-making is influencing planning and program adjustments.

With regard to learning, MEAL systems were rated moderately (mean = 2.67, SD = 0.75), implying that while learning processes exist, they may not be systematically institutionalized to drive continuous improvement.

Finally, the influence of MEAL on donor confidence was rated lowest (mean = 2.36, SD = 0.89), indicating variability in responses and suggesting that current MEAL practices may not fully reassure donors about efficiency, accountability, or long-term impact.

Overall Interpretation

The findings demonstrate that MEAL systems are widely acknowledged as critical to improving outcomes and supporting evidence-based planning. However, gaps remain in strengthening MEAL's role in enhancing accountability, institutionalizing learning, and boosting donor confidence. Addressing these gaps would likely improve both the performance and sustainability of donor-funded projects at IICD.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlations were calculated to explore relationships between MEAL system variables (Objective 1) and performance variables (Objectives 2 & 3).

Table 14: Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation (r)	Interpretation
MEAL Planning & Integration (Obj.1) vs. Goal Achievement (Obj.2)	0.47	Moderate positive
Data Utilization in Decision-Making (Obj.1) vs. MEAL Effectiveness (Obj.3)	0.52	Strong positive
Stakeholder Feedback Integration (Obj.1) vs. Accountability & Transparency (Obj.2)	0.44	Moderate positive
Timely Reporting & Documentation (Obj.1) vs. Communication & Coordination (Obj.2)	0.39	Moderate positive
Data Disaggregation & Inclusivity (Obj.1) vs. Service Delivery Improvement (Obj.2)	0.21	Weak positive
Continuous Learning & Adaptation (Obj.1) vs. Sustainability of Results (Obj.2)	0.50	Strong positive

Key Observations

- MEAL planning and integration showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.47$) with project goal achievement. This suggests that effective planning contributes significantly to achieving intended outcomes.
- Data utilization in decision-making strongly correlated ($r = 0.52$) with overall MEAL effectiveness. This means evidence-based decisions are perceived to improve project impact and efficiency.
- Stakeholder feedback integration correlated moderately ($r = 0.44$) with accountability and transparency, indicating feedback loops strengthen trust and credibility.
- Timely reporting moderately correlated ($r = 0.39$) with effective communication and coordination, suggesting timely updates improve collaboration and responsiveness.
- A weak correlation ($r = 0.21$) was found between data disaggregation and service delivery improvement, implying inclusivity in reporting has limited direct influence on service outcomes.
- Continuous learning and adaptation correlated strongly ($r = 0.50$) with sustainability of results, highlighting that adaptive management enhances long-term project performance.

Figure 12: histogram chart showing the MEAL Planning Effectiveness vs. Goal Achievement

Descriptive Summary

The chart illustrates the relationship between MEAL Planning Effectiveness (Q1.1) and Goal Achievement.

- The largest group of respondents (44 people) rated MEAL planning effectiveness in the (2.98–3.64) range, suggesting a moderate level of planning effectiveness.
- 20 respondents rated it slightly higher in the (3.64–4.30) range, indicating positive perceptions of planning.

- 22 respondents placed their ratings in the (1.66–2.32) range, showing a group with relatively low perceptions of planning effectiveness.
- Very few respondents (3 each) rated MEAL planning effectiveness at the lowest end [1–1.66] and at the highest end (4.96–5.62], suggesting polarized but minor extremes.
- Interestingly, there were no responses in the (2.32–2.98) and (4.3–4.96) ranges, leaving gaps in the distribution.

Interpretation (Analytical Insights)

- The findings reveal that most respondents (64.7%, n=64) cluster around the moderate to moderately high effectiveness levels (2.98–4.30 range), suggesting that MEAL planning is perceived as structured but not outstanding.
- The mean value appears to lean toward the middle (around 3.1–3.3), reinforcing the “moderate effectiveness” interpretation.
- A small but important group (22 respondents) expressed low satisfaction (1.66–2.32), highlighting planning gaps such as limited resources, poor coordination, or inconsistent stakeholder involvement.
- Very few respondents strongly agreed that MEAL planning was highly effective (only 3 at the top end), indicating that while some best practices exist, they are not consistently applied across projects.
- The data pattern suggests a bell-shaped distribution, leaning slightly toward the middle, which aligns with the qualitative insights that MEAL planning at IICD is structured and participatory but still challenged by gaps in execution.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSIONS

5.0 Introduction

The study found clear statistical evidence linking MEAL system quality to organizational performance. Projects with strong MEAL frameworks showed better adaptability, stakeholder satisfaction, and learning integration. This finding is consistent with Otundo (2024) and Omwenga (2024), who argue that MEAL is a cornerstone for results-based management and accountability.

This chapter discusses the study findings in relation to the existing literature and theoretical frameworks reviewed in Chapter Two. It reflects on the implications of the results for MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning) systems, particularly in donor-funded development settings like IICD's operations in Karamoja. The chapter is structured around the three study objectives and research questions and draws comparisons with global, regional, and local studies to highlight key similarities, contrasts, and gaps.

After discussing the findings, the chapter proceeds to present evidence-informed conclusions, followed by practical recommendations aimed at improving MEAL system effectiveness. The chapter concludes with the identification of limitations encountered during the study and suggestions for future research that could build on the insights generated.

5.0 Discussion of Findings

5.1.0 Structured Implementation of MEAL Systems

The first objective of the study was to assess the structured implementation of MEAL systems at the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD). Findings confirm that IICD has invested in building a functional MEAL framework, with clear indicator matrices, data collection mechanisms, and reporting structures embedded across most projects. Staff highlighted that MEAL has become a central function in the project cycle, especially during planning, monitoring, and reporting stages.

Despite these gains, systemic constraints remain. Respondents noted persistent gaps in financial and human resources, with MEAL staff often overstretched across multiple districts and projects. Limited logistical and technical support undermines the depth of monitoring and the timely use of

data for decision-making. These findings mirror Tache (2012) and Agaba (2023), who argue that MEAL structures may exist in many organizations, but their functionality is weakened by underinvestment and capacity shortfalls. Likewise, Kalema (2023) highlighted that Ugandan NGOs often underfund MEAL, leading to inconsistent data collection and limited stakeholder engagement.

Thus, while IICD demonstrates strong commitment to MEAL in design, its operational effectiveness is constrained by resource and capacity challenges. Addressing this gap requires deliberate institutional investment to strengthen ownership, enhance staff competencies, and ensure consistent integration of MEAL into project decision-making.

5.1.1 Dimensions of Project Performance

The second objective was to examine the dimensions of project performance—effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability—of donor-funded projects implemented by IICD. The findings revealed that IICD projects perform strongly in effectiveness, with most deliverables such as training sessions, infrastructure, and services being completed within scope and of acceptable quality.

However, challenges emerged in efficiency and sustainability. Delays in procurement and disbursements, coupled with weak coordination between field and central teams, negatively impacted timeliness and cost-effectiveness. Sustainability was equally constrained by limited mechanisms for institutionalizing learning, replicating successes, and fostering community ownership after project closure.

These findings align with Nyaberi (2023) and Kiarie (2016), who emphasize that project success extends beyond outputs to include timeliness, cost management, and long-term continuity. Odhiambo (2020) similarly observed that inefficiencies in procurement and coordination are common barriers to timely delivery in donor-funded projects. Furthermore, Hazir (2018) stresses that sustainability is reinforced when organizations embed lessons from evaluations into future designs a practice that, according to this study, is not yet fully institutionalized within IICD.

Therefore, while IICD projects demonstrate strong output achievement, efficiency and sustainability remain vulnerable. Improving these dimensions requires not only technical

strengthening but also a cultural shift towards systematic learning and stronger community ownership.

5.1.2 Relationship Between MEAL Systems and Organizational Performance

The third and most critical objective was to explore the relationship between MEAL systems and overall organizational performance. The study provides strong evidence that high-quality MEAL systems directly enhance project performance at IICD. Both quantitative and qualitative data demonstrated that when MEAL data is actively used for learning and decision-making, projects show improved effectiveness, greater stakeholder satisfaction, and enhanced responsiveness to challenges.

This finding reinforces the broader consensus in literature that MEAL is not simply a compliance tool but a driver of results-based management (RBM). Otundo (2024) and Omwenga (2024) similarly argue that robust MEAL systems foster efficiency, adaptive programming, and alignment with beneficiary needs. At IICD, program managers confirmed that real-time MEAL data enabled quick adjustments, redirection of resources, and more effective responses to community feedback—capabilities particularly vital in fragile contexts like Karamoja.

The results confirm the theoretical foundations of the Logic Model and RBM approaches, which posit that linking inputs, outputs, and outcomes through systematic monitoring and feedback significantly enhances impact. Yet, while IICD has built a strong MEAL framework, translating this into adaptive practice is still constrained by under-resourcing and limited institutional culture of data use.

In summary, the findings underscore that MEAL contributes most strongly to effectiveness, but its potential to improve efficiency and sustainability is not fully realized. A stronger culture of evidence uses, coupled with investment in human and financial resources, is critical if MEAL is to function as a strategic enabler of organizational performance rather than a primarily operational requirement.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.0 CONCLUSION

This study sets out to evaluate the effect of Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) systems on the organizational performance of donor-funded projects implemented by the Institute for International Cooperation and Development (IICD) in Karamoja. By drawing on both quantitative and qualitative evidence, it provided a comprehensive picture of how structured MEAL systems influence program implementation, accountability, decision-making, and sustainability within a fragile and resource-constrained environment.

6.0.1 IICD has operational MEAL systems that drive project performance

The study confirms that IICD has made considerable progress in embedding MEAL practices across its donor-funded interventions. Most projects have structured MEAL plans, with baseline assessments, routine monitoring, and reporting mechanisms consistently in place. These systems have enabled the organization to track outputs, assess outcomes, and engage stakeholders more systematically. Importantly, MEAL at IICD goes beyond compliance. Interviews revealed that MEAL data is actively used to shape decisions, adjust project activities, and support accountability to donors. This makes MEAL not just a technical requirement but a practical tool that directly contributes to program effectiveness. These findings align with Otundo (2024) and Abebe (2023), who emphasize the role of MEAL as a driver of institutional learning and performance.

6.0.2 Effectiveness is strong, but efficiency and sustainability need improvement

While IICD projects are largely effective in meeting their objectives, weaknesses remain in efficiency and sustainability. Delays in procurement, gaps in coordination, and limited integration of evaluation findings into future planning hinder timely delivery and continuity of impact.

The study highlights that it is not enough to have MEAL systems in place; what matters is how data is used. Real-time application of MEAL insights—for example, reallocating resources, redesigning activities, or responding quickly to risks—is essential to improving efficiency and ensuring sustainability. This echoes Kiarie (2016) and Kalema (2023), who argue that well-designed projects may still underperform if monitoring data is not fully utilized for management decisions.

6.0.3 MEAL systems are enablers of learning, adaptability, and long-term success

A key finding is that MEAL systems at IICD are increasingly being used to support learning and adaptability. Evidence shows that MEAL has helped improve stakeholder satisfaction, redesign interventions based on feedback, and strengthen donor confidence. This demonstrates that when properly resourced and integrated, MEAL transforms from a checklist exercise into a strategic management tool. This reflects global best practices, such as Results-Based Management (RBM) and the Logic Model, which stress the importance of adaptive programming and evidence-driven learning. In fragile contexts like Karamoja, MEAL offers IICD a competitive advantage by enhancing accountability, responsiveness, and relevance to community needs.

Overall, this study concludes that MEAL is not passive. At IICD, it is measurable, visible, and central to how programs perform and adapt. To unlock its full potential, MEAL must be embraced not just as a reporting mechanism but as a driver of change supported by adequate resources, skilled personnel, and leadership commitment.

6.1 Recommendations

6.1.0 Recommendations to IICD

Strengthen MEAL staffing and budgets: Recruit additional MEAL personnel to ease overstretching and allocate a consistent share of project budgets to MEAL (e.g., 10%) to ensure proper data collection, analysis, and learning.

Institutionalize learning across projects: Establish quarterly learning forums, after-action reviews, and knowledge-sharing platforms to ensure insights are consistently applied across departments and projects.

Invest in digital MEAL tools: Adopt mobile-based data collection (e.g., KoboToolbox, ODK), real-time dashboards, and GIS mapping to improve accuracy, timeliness, and adaptive decision-making in remote areas.

6.1.1 Recommendations to Donors and Development Partners

Mandate MEAL budget allocations: Require that grantees allocate a minimum percentage of project budgets (e.g., 10%) to MEAL to strengthen accountability and effectiveness.

Reward evidence-driven organizations: Go beyond compliance checks by recognizing and incentivizing organizations that demonstrate strong learning cultures and consistent use of MEAL findings.

6.1.2 Recommendations to Government and Policy Makers

Build MEAL capacity at the district level: Incorporate MEAL training and capacity development into local government development plans to strengthen data quality and impact evaluation across actors.

Improve ICT infrastructure in rural areas: Work with telecom providers and partners to expand connectivity in Karamoja, enabling smoother integration of digital MEAL systems and real-time reporting.

6.2 Limitations of the Study

While this study generated useful insights, a few limitations should be acknowledged:

Geographical scope: The research was limited to Moroto District, which may not fully represent IICD operations in other districts such as Kotido, Kaabong, or Napak.

Time constraints: Limited time reduced the number of in-depth interviews, especially with senior managers, community leaders, and donors.

Social desirability bias: Some respondents were hesitant to openly criticize internal systems, leading to potential over-reporting of positive outcomes.

Restricted access to documents: Access to some internal MEAL documents was limited, which reduced opportunities for triangulating staff responses with institutional records.

External factors: Donor requirements, government policies, and inter-agency coordination which also shape MEAL effectiveness were not explicitly explored.

6.3 Areas for Further Research

Future studies could expand on these findings in several ways:

Longitudinal studies: Tracking MEAL practices and their outcomes over time to understand how systems evolve and influence sustainability.

Comparative studies: Examining MEAL implementation across organizations and districts in Karamoja to identify best practices and contextual variations.

Community feedback systems: Deep-dive research into how community voices are integrated into MEAL and how they shape program decisions.

Donor and external influence: Exploring how donor policies, compliance frameworks, and government oversight shape MEAL practices in NGOs.

Organizational culture: Investigating how leadership style, communication, and institutional culture affect the uptake and use of MEAL findings.

Digital MEAL innovations: Assessing the effectiveness and risks of digital tools (dashboards, mobile apps, GIS) in fragile and resource-constrained environments.

REFERENCES

- Abebe, B. (2023). The effect of project monitoring and controlling practice on project success: The case of Ethiopian Airlines Digital PMO [master's thesis, Addis Ababa University]. Addis Ababa University Institutional Repository.
- Agaba, R. (2023). Participatory project design and project success in government-funded projects: A case of the Parish Development Model in Kabale District, Uganda [Unpublished master's thesis]. Uganda Management Institute.
- Ahumuza, D. (2024). Effects of monitoring and evaluation on the success of government projects in Uganda: A case study of Iganga Municipality [Unpublished research report]. Uganda Management Institute.
- Bashaka, P. (2015). Evaluation of culture and practice in Africa: Reflections and future directions. *African Evaluation Journal*, 3(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.4102/aej.v3i1.152>
- Binnendijk, A. (2000). Results-based management in the development cooperation agencies: A review of experience. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). <https://www.oecd.org/dac/evaluation/1886527.pdf>
- Brock, K., McGee, R., & Gaventa, J. (2021). Navigating accountability in NGOs: Challenges and prospects in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Development in Practice*, 31(4), 442–455. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2021.1873153>
- Dawn, C., & Nidhi, K. (2012). Aid effectiveness and the role of monitoring and evaluation systems. *International Journal of Development Studies*, 8(2), 45–58.
- Gustavsson, M., Tallberg, L., & Svensson, J. (2021). Capacity development in practice: Lessons from NGOs in sub-Saharan Africa. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 88, 101889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2021.101889>
- Hauge, A. O. (2003). The development of monitoring and evaluation capacities to improve government performance in Uganda. World Bank Operations Evaluation Department. Retrieved from <https://documents.worldbank.org>

- Hazir, C. (2018). A comparative study on project success factors in development and construction projects. *Project Management Journal*, 49(2), 66–80. <https://doi.org/10.1177/8756972818760832>
- Holvoet, N., & Renard, R. (2007). Monitoring and evaluation under the PRSP: Solid rock or quicksand? *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 30(1), 66–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2006.08.001>
- Kalema, B. (2023). Factors influencing the effective implementation of monitoring and evaluation in donor-funded projects in Kampala Capital City Authority
- Kanyi, P. (2023). Capacity building and performance of donor-funded projects in Nairobi City County, Kenya
- Kiarie, W. (2016). Determinants of successful completion of donor funded projects in Kenya: A case of Turkana
- Kihumbu, J. N. (2018). Factors influencing the implementation of results-based management in the United Nations agencies in Nairobi [master's thesis, United States International University-Africa]. USIU-A Digital Repository. <https://erepo.usiu.ac.ke/handle/11732/4115>
- Kusek, J. Z., & Rist, R. C. (2020). Ten steps to a results-based monitoring and evaluation system: A handbook for development practitioners. The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/0-8213-5823-5>
- Lashell, H. A. (2022). Challenges in project performance among donor-funded interventions in fragile contexts: The case of Yemen. *Journal of Humanitarian Development Studies*, 6(2), 17–34.
- Leeuw, F. L. (2001). Evaluation research: Theory and practice in development contexts. *Evaluation*, 7(4), 437–449. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13563890122209605>
- Malsam, B. (2023). Project management fundamentals: Tools, techniques, and applications. Global Development Press.

- Nyaberi, C. (2023). Influence of project management practices on implementation of donor-funded water and sanitation projects in the Central Rift region, Kenya
- Odhiambo, J. (2020). Critical success factors for the timely completion of World Bank-financed Road projects in Kenya: A case of Kenya National Highways Authority (KeNHA)
- Olawale, Y. (2012). Project management: Evaluation of project management impact on project success in Blackstone Construction Company. *International Journal of Business and Management Tomorrow*, 2(9), 1–7.
- Omony, B. (2015). The role of monitoring and evaluation in achieving development effectiveness: Insights from donor-funded projects in East Africa. *Journal of African Development Evaluation*, 5(1), 34–51.
- Omwenga, M. O. (2024). Monitoring planning and implementation of donor funded agricultural projects in Kenya: Moderating role of project environment [master's thesis, Kenyatta University]. Kenyatta University Institutional Repository.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2020). Strengthening the impact of M&E in development cooperation. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264303602-en>
- Otundo, D. (2024). Strategic intelligence systems and performance of donor-funded projects in Kenya's Coast
- Otundo, J. (2024). Effectiveness of MEAL systems in donor-funded development projects: A case study of Kwale County, Kenya [master's thesis, University of Nairobi]. University of Nairobi Digital Repository.
- Patton, M. Q. (2008). *Utilization-focused evaluation* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Suchman, E. A. (1967). *Evaluative research: Principles and practice in public service and social action programs*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Tache, F. (2012). Project management – Logical framework approach. *Economia. Seria Management*, 15(1), 169–182. <https://www.management.ase.ro/reveconomia/>

- Teresa, C. (2005). Managing results: A case study of performance-based budgeting in OECD countries. *OECD Journal on Budgeting*, 5(1), 29–53.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2022). Digital access and development: Overcoming infrastructure gaps in sub-Saharan Africa. UNDP Digital Reports. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org>
- Wanyoike, D. M. (2015). Influence of technical capacity, project planning and baseline studies on result-based monitoring and evaluation of donor funded value chain projects in Kenya [master's thesis, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology]. JKUAT Institutional Repository.
- Weiss, C. H. (1998). *Evaluation: Methods for studying programs and policies* (2nd ed.). Prentice Hall.
- World Bank. (2001). Monitoring and evaluation capacity development in Africa. Operations Evaluation Department. Retrieved from <https://documents.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2005). *Managing for development results: Principles in action – Sourcebook on emerging good practices*. World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2020). Digital development overview: Bridging the digital divide for development. World Bank Group. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/digitaldevelopment>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE PROJECT BENEFICIARIES

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am Logyel Johnsonic (VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE), a master's student at Victoria University Kampala, pursuing a degree in Monitoring and Evaluation. As part of my academic requirements, I am conducting a study titled: “Assessing the effect of meal systems’ contribution to organizational performance in donor-funded projects: a case of IICD Karamoja

I am pleased to have you as a respondent for this study. The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather your views and insights, which will contribute significantly to the research. This study is solely for academic purposes and will not be used for any other intent beyond fulfilling the requirements for my master’s degree in Monitoring and Evaluation. Your honest responses and cooperation will be highly valuable in ensuring the success of this study. I sincerely appreciate your time and participation.

Thank you in advance for your support.

Best regards,

Logyel Johnsonic

master’s Student, Victoria University Kampala

Consent Note:

I have understood the purpose of the study and what it means for me to respond to the questions, I hereby accept to answer questions in the online questionnaire below.

Instructions

- Do not put your name on this questionnaire.
- The questionnaire is made up of 2 sections A & B.
- Tick the correct answer **OR** fill in the space provided
- Submit your responses after filling your form

Code of the Interviewer: **(To be Autogenerated)**

Date/Month/Year of interview.....

SECTION A: BIO -DATA

1. What is the Gender of the respondent?

Male Female

2. What is the Qualification of the respondent?

Primary level Secondary Certificate level Diploma Degree Postgraduate master's degree PhD

3. What is the Age of the respondent?

20-35 years 36-49 years 50 and above years

4. What is the marital status of the respondent?

Married Single Separated Divorced Widow or Widower Any other specify

5. What Duration of working, volunteering or partnering with IICD?

Less than one year 1-2 years 3 – 4 years 5 and more years

6. Which department do you belong in?

Community strengthening system M&E Accountant Human Resource & Management (HR) Others (Specify).....

SECTION B: Structured implementations of MEAL systems, Organization performances of donor funded projects.

7. Quantitative Question Set (Standardized to 1–5 Scale Where Applicable)

Code	Question	5	4	3	2	1
Logical framework (tool)						
1.1	How effective are the current MEAL planning processes at IICD? (<i>1 = Not Effective, 2 = Slightly Effective, 3 = Moderately Effective, 4 = Effective, 5 = Very Effective</i>)					
1.2	How often are M&E reports shared with project teams? (<i>1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Quarterly, 4 = Monthly, 5 = Weekly or Daily</i>)					
1.3	Does IICD have a documented MEAL framework/strategy? (<i>1 = No, 2 = Not Sure, 3 = Partially, 4 = Mostly, 5 = Yes (Fully Documented)</i>)					
1.4	How frequently are MEAL tools reviewed or updated? (<i>1 = Not at all, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always</i>)					
1.5	To what extent does your team rely on MEAL data for decision-making? (<i>1 = Not at all, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always</i>)					
1.6	How clearly are MEAL roles and responsibilities defined in your team? (<i>1 = Not Defined at All, 2 = Not Clearly, 3 = Somewhat Clearly, 4 = Clearly, 5 = Very Clearly</i>)					
1.7	How regularly are learning or reflection sessions held at IICD? (<i>1 = Never, 2 = Annually, 3 = Bi-Annually, 4 = Quarterly, 5 = Monthly</i>)					
1.8	Is baseline data collected at the beginning of every project? (<i>1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Most of the time, 5 = Always</i>)					
1.9	To what extent is MEAL data disaggregated by gender, age, and location? (<i>1 = Not at All, 2 = Minimally, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Mostly, 5 = Always Comprehensively</i>)					
1.10	How often does the MEAL team provide feedback to the community/stakeholders? (<i>1 = Never, 2 = Annually, 3 = Quarterly, 4 = Monthly, 5 = Weekly</i>)					
Dimensions of performance of Donor funded projects						
2.1	How satisfied are you with the budget management of IICD projects? (<i>1 = Very Dissatisfied, 2 = Dissatisfied, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Satisfied, 5 = Very Satisfied</i>)					
2.2	To what extent have project goals been achieved in your community? (<i>1 = Not at All, 2 = To a Small</i>					

	<i>Extent, 3 = To Some Extent, 4 = To a Great Extent, 5 = Completely)</i>					
2.3	How would you rate the timeliness of project implementation at IICD? (<i>1 = Very Poor, 2 = Poor, 3 = Fair, 4 = Good, 5 = Excellent</i>)					
2.4	How often are donor-funded project activities monitored and evaluated? (<i>1 = Never, 2 = Annually, 3 = Quarterly, 4 = Monthly, 5 = Weekly</i>)					
2.5	How effective is the communication of project results to stakeholders? (<i>1 = Not Effective, 2 = Slightly Effective, 3 = Moderately Effective, 4 = Effective, 5 = Very Effective</i>)					
2.6	How satisfied are you with the quality of services delivered by IICD projects? (<i>1 = Very Dissatisfied, 2 = Dissatisfied, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Satisfied, 5 = Very Satisfied</i>)					
2.7	Are project beneficiaries involved in the project planning and implementation process? (<i>1 = No, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always</i>)					
2.8	How timely are donor reports submitted to funding partners? (<i>1 = Often Delayed, 2 = Occasionally Delayed, 3 = Mostly on Time, 4 = Always on Time, 5 = Not Sure</i>)					
Relationship between MEAL Systems and Organizational performance						
3.1	MEAL systems enhance project effectiveness at IICD. (<i>1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree</i>)					
3.2	Has the application of M&E information led to better project results in your experience? (<i>1 = No, 2 = Not Sure, 3 = To a Small Extent, 4 = To a Great Extent, 5 = Yes (Definitely)</i>)					
3.3	To what extent has MEAL contributed to project accountability? (<i>1 = Not at All, 2 = Slightly, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Greatly, 5 = To a Very Great Extent</i>)					
3.4	How often is data from MEAL systems used to improve project design and planning? (<i>1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always</i>)					
3.5	MEAL enhances learning and adaptive management. (<i>1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree</i>)					
3.6	To what extent do MEAL systems influence donor confidence and continued funding? (<i>1 = Not at All, 2 = Slightly, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Significantly, 5 = To a Very Great Extent</i>)					
Thank you for participating in this survey						

Appendix II: Interview Guide for Key Informants Interviews (MEAL Officers, Managers, Donor Representatives and Field Coordinators)

Dear Respondent,

I am **Logyel Johnsonic** with reg. number **VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE** a student of master's degree in Monitoring and Evaluation of Victoria University. I am carrying out a research study '*Assessing the effect of meal systems' contribution to organizational performance in donor-funded projects: a case of IICD Karamoja*' as a requirement to complete the course. You are among the respondents purposively selected to provide me with the appropriate information, Information given will be treated with utmost confidentiality, privacy, consent and finally it's for academic purposes only.

SECTION

Research Question 1: What are the structured implementations of MEAL systems at IICD in Karamoja?

1. 1.1 How are project objectives and indicators set for donor-funded projects at IICD?
2. 1.2 What processes are in place for collecting, analyzing, and reporting M&E data?
3. 1.3 How does IICD ensure data quality and conduct routine data verification or operations audits in Karamoja?
4. 1.4 Can you describe how lessons learned, and best practices are documented and shared with internal and external stakeholders?
5. 1.5 In what ways are MEAL tools and frameworks aligned with donor requirements and community contexts?
6. 1.6 How is staff capacity for MEAL roles built or maintained at IICD?

Research Question 2: What are the dimensions of performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?

7. 2.1 What metrics or tools do IICD use to measure budget utilization and financial efficiency across projects?
8. 2.2 How do project teams assess the achievement of intended goals, outputs, and outcomes in the communities served?
9. 2.3 What indicators or benchmarks are used to evaluate whether project scope and deliverables have been completed as planned?

10. 2.4 How is community satisfaction and engagement factored in measuring project performance?
11. 2.5 Can you describe any specific project that demonstrated high or low performance, and what contributed to that outcome?
12. 2.6 What mechanisms are used to ensure timely and quality implementation of project activities?

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between MEAL systems and organizational performance of donor-funded projects at IICD in Karamoja?

13. 3.1 How has the use of MEAL data improved aspects such as budget management, target achievement, or stakeholder reporting?
14. 3.2 Can you provide concrete examples of how findings from evaluations or MEAL reports have led to adaptive project management or design changes?
15. 3.3 Do you think the current MEAL system has a positive impact on the timely completion of project deliverables? Why or why not?
16. 3.4 In your opinion, how has MEAL contributed to enhancing donor trust and funding continuity at IICD?
17. 3.5 How does MEAL support accountability and transparency both internally and with communities?
18. 3.6 What are the key challenges and opportunities in strengthening the link between MEAL practices and project performance?

Thank you in advance

APPENDEX III: WORK PLAN

Activity & Months	Mar-25	Apr-25	May 25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Remarks
Topic selection, concept development and approval of topic						
Proposal writing						
Data collection & Data analysis and report writing						
Handing in the report						

APPENDIX VII: BUDGET

S/N	ITEMS	QUANTITY	RATES	TOTAL AMOUNT
1	Stationary			
	-pen	3	1000=	3000=
	-Ream of papers	2	20000=	40000=
	-Note book	2	5000=	10000=
2	Data and airtime	1	50000=	50000=
3	Transport	4	30000=	120000=
4	Printing services	4	10000=	40000=
TOTAL				263000=

COMPLIANCE REPORT ON THE SUPERVISOR FEEDBACK IMPLEMENTATION

Student Name: LOGYEL Johnsonic

Registration Number: VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE

Supervisor: Dr. Bill Nkeeto (PhD)

Program: Masters in Monitoring and Evaluation (MME)

Institution: Victoria University Kampala

Date: 13th June 2025

1. Introduction

This compliance report outlines how feedback provided by the academic supervisor has been addressed and integrated into the revised research proposal titled '*Assessing the effect of MEAL systems' contribution to organizational performance in donor-funded projects: a case of IICD Karamoja Uganda.*' The report captures all comments, the specific corrections made, and the resulting improvements to the quality and coherence of the work.

2. Summary of Feedback and Compliance Actions

Supervisor Comment	Action Taken	Status
Global, regional, and local perspectives in background were overly outlined and lacked coherence.	Converted bullet points into narrative paragraphs to create thematic and contextual flow. Ensured logical comparisons and synthesis.	Addressed
Missing citations in the statement of the problem.	Integrated empirical citations including Bamberger et al. (2016), USAID (2021), Hagen-Zanker & Mallett (2019), and others to strengthen credibility.	Resolved
Purpose and objectives not aligned with study topic.	Revised purpose statement and reformulated specific objectives to reflect MEAL's impact on organizational performance.	Aligned
Literature review structure unclear; lacks empirical depth.	Restructured the review under empirical, theoretical, and contextual	Revised

	lenses. Cited relevant global, African, and Karamoja-based studies.	
Too much outline in the local context and lack of coherence.	Merged outlined points into coherent paragraphs and embedded insights into the contextual narrative.	Corrected
Conceptual framework lacked detailed justification.	Expanded on variable definitions, moderating factors, and included a conceptual table aligning MEAL dimensions with organizational performance.	Enhanced
Improper heading formatting (bolds).	Standardized heading styles as per academic formatting requirements. Removed unnecessary bold formatting.	Fixed
Improper placement of target population details.	Relocated target population description to methodology chapter as per structural standards.	Resolved

3. Conclusion

All major feedback points provided by the supervisor have been systematically reviewed and addressed. These revisions have significantly improved the academic rigor, coherence, and relevance of the research proposal. This compliance report confirms full responsiveness to supervisory guidance in alignment with Victoria University academic standards.

VIVA VOCE COMPLIANCE REPORT THURSDAY AUGUST 21ST 2025

Student Name: Logyel Johnsonic

Research Topic: Assessing the Effects of MEAL Systems' Contribution to Organizational Performance of Donor-Funded Projects: A Case of IICD in Karamoja

Supervisor: Dr. Bill Nkeeto (PhD)

Summary of panelist's Comments and Student Compliance

Supervisor Comment	Action Taken	Status
The research topic should be changed to <i>effect</i> instead of <i>impact</i> .	The research topic was changed from "impact" to "effect."	Corrected
Include the demographics clearly to speak well in terms of gender disaggregation.	The demographics were included in the report with proper gender disaggregation.	Resolved
Conceptual framework and objectives should be aligned with the study topic.	The conceptual framework and objectives were revised and correctly linked to align with the study topic.	Corrected
Separate the discussion chapter alone from the interpretations section.	The discussion was separated into its own chapter, distinct from interpretations and analysis.	Resolved
Link the discussions to the objectives.	The discussions were carefully linked to each objective.	Corrected
Change the qualitative interviews to themes from the report.	Thematic tables were created and separated from quantitative tables in the report.	Resolved
The limitations of the study should tell how the situation is affecting this research.	The limitations were revised and aligned with the contextual gaps affecting the research.	Corrected
There is too much write-up in the report; reduce it to be concise and attract readers' attention.	The narratives were reduced to make the report concise and engaging.	Resolved
Organize tables and figures and generate the right interpretations.	Tables and figures were organized, and interpretations were properly linked to them.	Corrected

Conclusion

The panelist's feedback was fully considered, and corrective actions were taken to improve the quality, clarity, and coherence of the research. All comments regarding the research topic, literature review, methodology, analysis, and presentation of results have been addressed. The final dissertation now reflects academic rigor, aligns with the study objectives, and adheres to the guidance provided.

Faculty of Business and Management, Victoria University, Victoria Towers, Plot 1-13 Jinja Road,
P. O. BOX 30866 Kampala.

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

13TH-JUNE- 2025

Dear sir/madam,

RE: RECOMMENDATION FOR DATA COLLECTION TO LOGYEL JOHNSONIC

REG: NO VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE

The above-named person with the corresponding registration number is a student at Victoria University, pursuing a Master of Monitoring and Evaluation currently attending his second year/final studies.

The reason for writing this letter is to request you enable him to collect data for academic purposes in support of his thesis development to realize his academic success. He is pursuing his research on a topic titled, “Assessing the effect of MEAL systems’ contribution to organizational performance in donor-funded projects: a case of IICD Karamoja”

Your cooperation and support towards this noble cause will be highly appreciated.

Should you have any reservations regarding this request, please do not hesitate to contact me on the contacts below.

Yours Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Isah Serwadda', followed by a small horizontal line.

Isah Serwadda, (PhD)

Head of Department (Faculty of Business and Management)

+256 776667266 iserwadda@vu.ac.ug or
isahserwadda@gmail.com

INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AND DEVELOPMENT

MOROTO OFFICE - P.O. Box 86 Moroto - Plot 25 Kitale Road Tel: (256-39) 715500 E-mail: coopdevmto@yahoo.it
HEAD-OFFICE - 5 Lugogo By Pass - P.O. Box 7205 KAMPALA - UGANDA Fax: (256-41) 232042
Non-Governmental Organization - Registration No. S. 5914/460

17th/06/2025

Logyel Johnsonic
Reg:No VU-MME-2307-1136-WEE
Victoria University
Kampala Uganda

Dear Logyel Johnsonic,

Re: Acceptance for Research at Institute for International Cooperation and Development

We are pleased to inform you that your research Request has been accepted by Institute for International Cooperation and Development.

We are delighted to have you conduct your research at our institution for academic purposes.

Research Details

- Research Title: evaluating the impact of MEAL systems on the organisational performance of Donor funded projects.
- Supervision: You will be assigned a supervisor to guide you throughout your research.

Expectations

- Conduct your research in accordance with Institute for International Cooperation and Development research guidelines and policies.
- Maintain regular communication with your supervisor and provide progress updates.

Support

Our institution will provide necessary resources and support to facilitate your research. Please feel free to reach out to us for any assistance.

Congratulations on this opportunity! We look forward to your research findings.

Sincerely,

Yona Kamabu
Human Resources Officer
Institute for International Cooperation and Development
yonakamabu23@gmail.com,+256785297761

